

KAIROUAN, OR A TALE OF THE CRITIC HAUSENSTEIN AND THE PAINTER KLEE

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SUMMARY

Easily the most unconventional monograph on a living artist to be published in Germany during the interwar period, Wilhelm Hausenstein's Klee monograph, *Kairuan* (1921), is paradoxically at once an encomium to Klee and a bleak jeremiad of cultural despair about modern art. Critic and artist operated from vastly different and incompatible presuppositions – and aspirations – about the possibilities for art in modernity, and the tension between the two epitomized the gap between Klee's attitudes and prac-

tice and the utopian hopes of the avant-garde in Germany. Ultimately Hausenstein's Klee monograph is a tale of its author more than of the painter, a product of the critic's struggle to theorize his strongly positive aesthetic response to an art that was antithetical to his hopes and most deeply held values. It is Hausenstein who is the focus of this essay; this is a tale about him, about his evolving response to Klee's art and the conflict it generated within himself.

Artistic creation and art criticism belong together, like punch and counterpunch; and whoever writes art history without showing the mirror image of art criticism in addition to the image of art-making removes art from the vital blood flow of life and reduces it to an artifact.

Albert Dresdner, *Die Kunstkritik*, 1915

In May 1920 the Munich gallery Neue Kunst Hans Goltz opened what at the time must surely have been the largest retrospective exhibition ever given to a European artist just entering mid-career – 387 objects. The artist was Paul Klee, who had just turned forty. Remarkably, the show comprised sixteen percent of his total recorded production to date – the modest dimensions of his works al-

lowed for such a generous survey.¹ Apart from thirty-eight paintings and six small painted plaster sculptures, all the works were on paper, over two-thirds of them produced since 1915.

With few exceptions these later works were free inventions, displaying a wide range of styles and motifs, most defying traditional categories of genre. A substantial number were completely abstract

Fig. 1
Paul Klee, *Farbenwinkel* [Coloured Angles], 1917, 50, watercolor, pen and pencil on paper on cardboard, 19.1 x 13.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Livia Klee Donation
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Fig. 2
Paul Klee, *Fata morgana zur See* [Fata Morgana at Sea], 1918, 12, watercolor and pen on paper on cardboard, 12.7 x 14.9 cm, San Francisco Museum of Modern Art, extended loan and promised gift of the Carl Djerassi Art Trust I
Photo: Don Ross/courtesy SFMOMA

Fig. 3
Paul Klee, *Komposition mit Fenstern* [Composition with Windows], 1919, 156, oil and pen on cardboard; original frame, 50.4 x 38.3 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 4
 Paul Klee, *Barbarische Komposition* [*Barbarian Composition*], 1918, 68, watercolor and gouache on paper on cardboard, 18.5 x 11.8/11.4 cm, location unknown
 Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

Fig. 5
 Paul Klee, *Versunkene Landschaft* [*Sunken Landscape*], 1918, 108, watercolor on primed linen on cardboard, 17 x 20 cm, private collection
 Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

Abb. 6
 Paul Klee, *Drei Gequälte* (bläul., rosa, gelbl.) [*Three Tormented Ones* (Blueish, Pink, Yellowish)], 1918, 16, pen and watercolor on paper on cardboard, 10.2 x 16.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Livia Klee Donation
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(FIG. 1); others were equally so but with titles that evoked representational associations (FIG. 2). Still others were abstract but with the interpolation of isolated figural elements, divorced from a natural or logical spatial syntax (FIGS. 3, 4). Many works were more fantastical, with simple ideographic signs for figures, vegetation, architectural elements and celestial bodies, often seemingly as a kind of associative afterthought for abstract, cubistic compositions (FIG. 5). Some drawings and watercolors were crudely primitive, seemingly nihilistic in both style and imagery, like a travesty of serious art (FIG. 6). According to

the printed catalog more than half of the watercolors and a quarter of the drawings, including some with figurative elements, were shown with no titles at all, with the column beside the date left blank (FIG. 7).

This vast public offering inspired an unusual response from one critic who, while decidedly favorable, found Klee as an artist to be “unsocial, exclusive, monomaniacal (*unsozial, exklusiv, monoman*).” He wondered: should such works be exhibited at all? “In the case of this artist to exhibit is a makeshift action. This art is not of a public nature. It is the most private of the private.” It belonged “above all

Fig. 7
Page with partial listing of watercolors from Klee's 1920 exhibition at Neue Kunst Hans Goltz, Munich, Paul Klee, in: *Der Ararat. Zweites Sonderheft* [60. exhibition, Galerie Neue Kunst Hans Goltz, May-June 1920], p. 22, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
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57	1914/16	*Schaffendes Haupt	102	1915/57
58	1914/22	Villen zu verkaufen	103	1915/71
59	1914/27	*Dampfer im Hafen	104	1915/115
60	1914/32	*St. Germain	105	1915/116
61	1914/36	Skizze aus Tunis	106	1915/130
62	1914/38		107	1915/148 Knabe am Pult
		Eigentum: Herr Goyert	108	1915/150
63	1914/45	*Rote und weiße Kuppeln	109	1915/152
64	1914/48	Motiv aus Hammamet	110	1915/184
65	1914/58	Die Hoffnungslosen	111	1915/218
66	1914/71	Hammamet	112	1915/220 Gold
67	1914/85	Das grüne Kreuz	113	1915/221
68	1914/86	Pflanzen auf der Terrasse	114	1915/225
69	1914/93		115	1916/11
70	1914/94		116	1916/13 *
71	1914/98	Blauer Kegel	117	1916/14
72	1914/103		118	1916/20 *Schriftbild
73	1914/104		119	1916/22 *Schriftbild
74	1914/109	Auf der Düne von St. Germain	120	1916/71 *Forellenbach
			121	1916/76
75	1914/114	Unfertiger Stadtteil	122	1917/2
76	1914/115	*Park	123	1917/26
77	1914/123		124	1917/29 Triebkraft des Waldes
78	1914/124		125	1917/39
79	1914/129		126	1917/40
80	1914/131		127	1917/42
81	1914/136	Mit der roten Zehn	128	1917/49
82	1914/139	Mit der roten Kuppel	129	1917/50
83	1914/145	*Park	130	1917/51
84	1914/147		131	1917/52 Gelb, blau violett
85	1914/148		132	1917/56
86	1914/149		133	1917/65 Die Himmelssäule
87	1914/170	Vorstadt	134	1917/70
88	1914/181	Tischgesellschaft	135	1917/77
89	1914/199	*Hammamet mit der Moschee	136	1917/86
90	1914/202	*Park in Kairuan	137	1917/87
91	1915/31	*Lachende Gotik	138	1917/90
92	1915/32		139	1917/99 Plan zu einem Haus
93	1915/33		140	1917/100
94	1915/34		141	1917/111
95	1915/35		142	1917/115
96	1915/38		143	1917/124 Mit dem Aussichtsberg
97	1915/46	Eine Erinnerung	144	1917/126
98	1915/51		145	1917/127 *Die Kapelle
99	1915/54		146	1917/128
100	1915/55		147	1917/131 Barbarenkönig
101	1915/56		148	1917/135 Mit dem schwarzen Blick

Fig. 8
 Front cover of Wilhelm Hausenstein, *Kairuan
 oder die Geschichte vom Maler Klee*, München
 1921
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

to itself: to its own intimacy. It belongs further to those who have an affinity for it. To exhibit here can only mean: to grant to the attentive an opportunity – and perhaps wait and see whether from afar one or two or others will appear.”² The critic was Wilhelm Hausenstein, and he unequivocally included himself among the elite endowed with this affinity – “with every fiber my feelings say yes.”³

To say “yes” to Klee contradicted Hausenstein’s most deeply cherished hopes for modern art. “Private” had long been a pejorative term in his vocabulary – it was identified with capitalism, individualism, the loss of a common culture of shared values and beliefs, the marginalization of art in this fragmented social fabric. For him the decisive question had been “whether the artist serves a community or is only the provider of individual delectation, the *maître de plaisir* for the sublime private enthusiasms of the indi-

vidual – whether one remains subordinate to collective concepts of beauty or sacrifices oneself to the subjective aestheticisms of an art anchorite averse to all communal life.”⁴ Modern art was “devoid of an organized social basis”; it “lacks the notion of a *public*. [...] Our public is reduced to the frictions between a thousand capitalistic private enterprises. No public art can flourish under such conditions [original emphasis].”⁵

Yet in the years preceding the war Hausenstein was nevertheless optimistic about the future of art: modern artists, he was confident, were turning away from individualism and were seeking new conventions, “the conventions of the future.” “Perhaps,” he mused, “we are moving toward a period in which painting, in which art, more than ever is a thing of tradition-rich collectives, not of blazing individuals, [...] in which single artists with their individual desires serve less their own solitude than a corporative idea of style as those in the Gothic era once did. The new art will culminate in a new anonymity.”⁶

But by 1920 Hausenstein’s optimistic expectations had collapsed, giving way to an ever darkening interpretation of modern art as a reflection of a profound cultural and spiritual crisis. The work of Paul Klee was central to this denouement. It was the subject of a monograph, *Kairuan, oder eine Geschichte vom Maler Klee und von der Kunst dieses Zeitalters* (*Kairuan, or a tale of the painter Klee and of the art of this time*) (FIG. 8).⁷ Easily the most unconventional monograph on a living artist to be published in Germany during the interwar period, *Kairuan* is, paradoxically, at once an encomium to Klee and a bleak jeremiad of cultural despair. In the starkest terms Hausenstein described what he saw as the crisis and Klee’s response to it: “We have entered the epoch of anarchy and disgregation. The subjective is truly not the highest. But at this moment it is the only thing; and the artist who is able to

find therein the beauty of rhyme is a miracle of heaven. [...] It is unthinkable that art, should it have the significance and beauty of consistency, look different than Klee's drawing, whose limits lie in the range of the excesses of his subjectivity. [...] The painter-draughtsman Klee took from his time what it was: he saw what it was not: saw its vacuum, its fissures, saw its ruins and sat above them. His name represents no system. His art is irrational, naïve even in its most sophisticated deliberations, it is faithful to the unheard-of confusion of the age."⁸ This dystopian view of modern art was the inverse of the utopian vision Hausenstein had held only a few years before. Klee, the *Ruinenmaler*, represented the extreme antithesis of that earlier vision.⁹ This disillusionment produced the dark state of mind in which Hausenstein wrote *Kairuan*.

There were other Weimar-era critics who wrote insightfully on Klee – Carl Einstein, Will Grohmann, Paul Westheim, to cite some of the more noteworthy – but among his contemporaries Hausenstein was the one who most acutely recognized both his artistic radicality and his anomalousness; how, quietly and indirectly, the character of his art was impervious to the most utopian hopes and aspirations of the avant-garde. Among German critics it was he, in his early writings, who offered the most eloquent articulation of those hopes and aspirations: the restoration of art to a central place in the life of the entire people; a collective, unified style transcending individual expression; a new religiosity; an overcoming of the narrow aestheticism of *l'art pour l'art*; a reintegration of painting with architecture, bringing an end to art's degraded status as a commodity under capitalism. These ideas were variously expressed by some of Klee's colleagues in the Blaue Reiter and the Bauhaus, most prominently in the persons of Walter Gropius, Wassily Kandinsky, Franz Marc, and Oskar

Schlemmer. Beyond their differences these individuals shared an optimistic vision of modernity in which art would have broad cultural agency, and this belief influenced their respective practices. Each of them, looking to a past in which art ostensibly had a secure, central place in the common culture, strove to restore a *public* role for art.¹⁰ They were driven by what the historian Peter Gay called "the hunger for wholeness."¹¹

Klee was more sober. Early on he had reconciled himself to the fragmented culture of modernity and to the marginality of traditional visual media within it. At age twenty-one, while on an extended study trip to Italy, he shared with his parents his melancholy realization that, in contrast to what he called the "paradise" of ancient art, "our art plays a very insignificant role in our culture. But no matter, this is how one came into the world, and one comes to terms with it."¹² The contrast with Hausenstein is stark. In the words of his biographer Johannes Werner, Hausenstein had from his youth manifested "the will to anticipate reality and to see what he wanted to see."¹³ A friend, the painter Richard Seewald, recalled that Hausenstein lived always in a "fictive world."¹⁴ His fictive world was shaped by his susceptibility to grand historiographic theories, and by projections – and longings – about the future of art. Ultimately, when modern art failed to meet his expectations, it became a casualty of his magical thinking.¹⁵ Klee's art embodied and often thematized certain conditions of the artistic culture of modernity that induced Hausenstein's despair; he embraced and adapted his art to those conditions. The tension between the two men epitomized the gap between Klee's attitudes and practice and the utopian hopes of the avant-garde in Germany. Yet despite their antithetical views I have found Hausenstein's writing on Klee rich in insights; reading him makes Klee's now comfortably familiar art strange

again, reveals its radicality anew. For me it has opened up a perspective for rethinking Klee's place in the German art world of his time and of what we call "modernism" more generally.¹⁶

In 1915, the Berlin art historian Albert Dresdner published the first volume of a planned three-volume historical study of art criticism.¹⁷ Writing at a time when "the confusion in the visual arts has reached a highpoint," he claimed the power and influence of art criticism to be at its peak. Accordingly, it followed that just as much as the art that was its object, art criticism demanded to be studied historically as "an independent organic phenomenon of intellectual life in the past and present, to be grasped, understood and judged on the basis of its own presuppositions."¹⁸ In the case of Hausenstein and Klee the mutual independence of their endeavors is especially striking: they were operating from vastly different and incompatible presuppositions – and aspirations – about the possibilities for art in modernity; Hausenstein assessed Klee's art from a position profoundly at odds with the artist's own. This latent friction between artist and critic ultimately found expression, I shall argue, in one of the artist's most famous works, *Angelus Novus*. Thanks to the allegorical interpretation of its original owner, Walter Benjamin, the work has become widely known as the "Angel of History."¹⁹ Building on a recent discovery and new research about this work, I will propose that *Angelus Novus* might have had a personal allegorical meaning for Klee: a playful rebuttal of Hausenstein's views regarding the future of painting.

Ultimately Hausenstein's *Kairuan* is a tale of its author more than of the painter Klee; he is the book's true protagonist. It is a product of his struggle to theorize his strongly positive aesthetic response to an art that was antithetical to his hopes and most deeply held values; Klee's art was a guilty pleasure, seductive and irresistible.

Thus it is Hausenstein who is the focus of this essay; this is a tale about him, about his evolving response to Klee's art and the conflict it generated within himself.²⁰

Wilhelm Hausenstein was born in the small town of Hornberg in the Black Forest in 1882. After the death of his father in 1891 he and his mother moved to Karlsruhe. In 1900, after receiving his *Abitur*, he enrolled at the University of Heidelberg. Raised in the Lutheran faith, his initial plan was to study theology, but he ultimately focused on philology and philosophy. At Heidelberg he also attended lectures in art history by Henry Thode, a scholar of Italian Renaissance art.²¹ In the summer of 1903 Hausenstein moved to the University of Munich, from which he earned a doctorate *summa cum laude* in history in 1905.²²

Through his friend and classmate Theodor Heuss (who went on to become the first President of the Federal Republic of Germany) Hausenstein became familiar with the writings of the art critic Julius Meier-Graefe. The publication of his three-volume *Entwicklungsgeschichte der modernen Kunst* (Evolutionary history of modern art) in 1904 was a momentous event in the Germanophone art world, and Hausenstein's encounter with it and other writings by the critic was a major factor in his own turn to art criticism.²³ He revered Meier-Graefe as his mentor, lauding him as "the writer [...] who more than any other has powerfully understood the genealogy of modern painting," one "to whom Germany and art-historical world literature owe a tremendous debt of gratitude."²⁴ Meier-Graefe was the foremost German advocate of French Impressionism and Post-Impressionism, and this advocacy went hand in hand with a brutal critique of German art's penchant for the literary. There were "two

traditions," he wrote, "the one relatively artistic," engaged with questions of form, "the other relatively literary. The former is, of course, the only essential one from our standpoint. [...] Its capital, its principal residence, we may say, is at present Paris."²⁵ Yet even as he lauded the achievements of recent painting in France, Meier-Graefe presented a sober critical assessment of art's status in modernity: "Art has become free; it has thrown off, not only the bondage of the Church, but that of all subsequent elements that have attempted more or less successfully to take the place of the religious impulse. Today art is as essentially the work of the individual as it was formerly that of thousands. It has changed so much that the name it once bore is scarcely applicable now. Between the new and the old are gaps as great as those that divide the individual and the mass. These are separate concepts that no art history can weld together."²⁶ Such was Meier-Graefe's view of the elite, isolated status of European art in modernity.

Earlier in the book he elaborated on this view: "In earlier times [art] was for everyone, since it belonged to no one. It stood above the greed of the individual, was an extremely communistic sign in a time that was otherwise far removed from the socialism of our day. Today it has become the very expression of our terrible class distinctions. It is only accessible to an aristocracy, whose domination is the more sinister, in that it is not based solely on rank and wealth, that is to say, on things by the division of which the bold socialist hopes to re-establish the social equilibrium. [...] Nowadays, one must not only have a great deal of money to buy art, one must be an exceptional creature, of peculiar gifts, to enjoy it. It exists only for the few, and these are far from being the most admirable or beneficent of mankind; they seem, indeed, to show all the characteristics of the degenerate.

Loftiness of character, or of intelligence, are not essential to the comprehension of art. The greatest men of our age have notoriously known nothing about it."²⁷

Hausenstein shared Meier-Graefe's grim assessment of the debased, marginal status of art in modernity – its commodification, its elitism, the decline of community and of social integration that came with secularization and artistic freedom. But he was also a "bold socialist," committed to "re-establish the social equilibrium." In 1907 he joined the German Social Democratic Party (SPD), effectively closing off the possibility of an academic career.²⁸ He became a prolific author, publishing regularly in the independent journal *Sozialistische Monatshefte*, for which he served as cultural editor, and other socialist periodicals. And not only did he write: from 1908 to 1915 he offered night courses in political and cultural history to workers in a Munich school operated by the Social Democratic Party.²⁹ At one point he planned a series of pedagogical pamphlets on art history aimed at a working-class readership.³⁰ Hausenstein's firm conviction of the inevitable triumph of socialism made him optimistic about the future of art, an art that would overcome those "terrible class distinctions" that Meier-Graefe evidently considered virtually unbridgeable. This faith was combined, seemingly paradoxically, with a belief in an emergent new religiosity. Hausenstein engaged with these ideas in a series of articles and in two books, *Der nackte Mensch in der Kunst aller Zeiten und Völker* (The Nude human figure in the art of all times and peoples, 1913) and *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart* (Visual art of the present, 1914).³¹

In *Der nackte Mensch* Hausenstein proposed a reorientation of the historical study of art from an emphasis on individual artists to a critical examination of form as socially determined. It was a blueprint for a sociology of style – he

called it a *Sozialästhetik*, a social aesthetics.³² The individualism of artistic achievements from the Renaissance to the present as well as the art-historical discourse celebrating them were products of bourgeois capitalism. Both were committed to the idea of art as an “expression of the emancipated personality.”³³ This cult of the individual artist, Hausenstein countered, was based on a “grotesque fiction,” an excrescence of a capitalism that prized individual entrepreneurship. Artistic style, as a collective expression, had been a casualty of this culture of individualism: “The idea of style rigorously conceived means the firmly unified synthesis of all forms of existence. [...] Style is the most hostile form of opposition to the principle of individualism.”³⁴ Convinced of the imminent triumph of socialism, Hausenstein believed that it would create the conditions for a longed-for unified style. “The art of our day is a catastrophe for naturalism and the victory of style.” This was the opening sentence of *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart*.³⁵

Hausenstein elaborated on his views in a long article, “Versuch einer Soziologie der bildenden Kunst” (Attempt at a sociology of visual art) in a social science journal edited by Max Weber.³⁶ There he presented a compact survey of the evolving relation between worldview, social structure, and artistic form from prehistoric times, culminating in what he described as the fallen state of European art in the bourgeois nineteenth century. No longer a living phenomenon with a broad cultural foundation, “art became historical. [...] There arose the painting of ‘as if.’ Ingres perfected the line that David had begun and made of it a document of the most personal culture. Delacroix painted as if the bourgeoisie of Louis-Philippe were the public of Titian and Veronese.” Art became “a specialty of the studio, participating in the process of individuation and the division of labor. [...] Art became a pri-

vate thing,” an “individual matter,” when by its nature it should be a social expression.³⁷ Hausenstein, optimistic socialist that he was, convinced himself that this was now changing.

Meier-Graefe was reconciled to art’s status as “a private thing,” and herein lay a major difference with Hausenstein. The crucial question for the modern art consumer, Meier-Graefe wrote, was, “Can I hang this picture in my house?” For him this situation encapsulated “the tragedy of today’s art,” the lack of a connection between artist and consumer, since modern artists could not know for whom or what or where their work was destined. Hence, the savvy artist should make the work as mobile, as adaptable as possible, and thus more saleable “as a commodity, as a medium of exchange.”³⁸ But Meier-Graefe also saw a positive development in the modern art economy: the institution of the museum, which “in virtually ideal form” replaced church and the court as a destination for the artwork. The museum was a “completely neutral space serving only beauty.” It “knows no other purpose – nor does it need to know one.” It had “all the elements of an institution of which we can be proud.”³⁹

For Hausenstein the mere existence of public art collections was depressing proof of art’s fallen state. “Museums, painting galleries, sculpture collections, formal repositories of art, can only come into existence where artistic production has lost the connection with the daily apparatus of the life of the individual and of the collective.”⁴⁰ Looking back nostalgically to the Baroque and the Rococo, he longed for a return of the “immobile picture,” for an era “when pictures knew where they belonged. They did not wander about lost and devoid of function like the pictures of the nineteenth century”; they had a secure place in the “cultural apparatus of the time.”⁴¹ He was conspicuously

silent on exactly how this revival of the immobile artwork might come about.⁴²

At 345 pages *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart* was the most extensive examination of recent European art to appear in Germany before the war and the most substantive survey in German in the decade since Meier-Graefe's *Entwicklungsgeschichte*. Its fifteen-chapter survey began with German Realism and French Impressionism and concluded with Cubism and Futurism. With it Hausenstein established himself as one of the most passionate, eloquent advocates for the newest European art. Like many German critics of the time he labeled this art "expressionism," which he defined broadly as "the art that more than any art up to our day strongly and consciously deforms natural appearances."⁴³ The term encompassed not only art produced in Germany and Austria but also that of the Fauves, the Cubists, and the Futurists.⁴⁴

Yet for Hausenstein "expressionism" had a significance that went beyond the art world: it was the vanguard of a radical social and cultural transformation. It was, he was confident, preparing the way for a future that would bring about a collective, democratic artistic expression and social reconciliation between the classes. For him the new anti-naturalistic art was a sign "that we are moving toward a new feeling for the world: a feeling of a religious kind."⁴⁵ By religion Hausenstein understood not necessarily a sectarian creed but a "feeling for the world that sees in every thing a discrete fragment of infinity and extends every thing beyond its own limits."⁴⁶ Although one could not predict the future form of this religion, he expressed confidence that "its artistic expression will not exhaust itself in the naturalistic representation of natural facts, but [in] the mysticism of things."⁴⁷ This spiritual turn did not mean the triumph of individual subjective expression however,

for the new art, unlike Impressionism, had an objective idea of order. "The new artist does not care to appeal to his individuality. He appeals to the objective laws of art. He appeals to the transpersonal requirements of style."⁴⁸

Paul Klee was a decidedly awkward fit for Hausenstein's concept of Expressionism. In 1912, presenting his own views on the newest art, which he, too, called "expressionism," he hailed modernity as "a facilitation of individuality," in which "everyone is driven all the more to become a pronounced self."⁴⁹ This was precisely that "expression of the emancipated personality" that Hausenstein hoped Expressionism would relegate to the past. Indeed, from the beginning Klee and the committed socialist Hausenstein made for an odd, uneasy pairing. Klee's early diaries and letters sometimes betrayed an attitude of condescension toward the working class.⁵⁰ But in 1905, after reading Oscar Wilde's idiosyncratic essay "The Soul of Man under Socialism," he wrote to his fiancée, Lily Stumpf, that it demonstrated "that socialism and individualism could be fused, that the artist could be a socialist."⁵¹ Yet this was an elitist socialism: "One must seek humanity only in its cultural peaks in order to achieve respect for it. If socialism wants and is able to provide every talent with a proper milieu then I too am a socialist. Yet here I lack faith, as I do in most things. But I would never be against it, because it is the only decent movement."⁵²

Klee's faith was short lived – four months later he lamented to Lily: "My hopelessness that humankind could ever be bettered cannot be greater. [...] I wish only to enlighten; nothing is salvageable. Even socialism is merely alms. Just as in our day charity within the capitalist system is merely alms, so, too, a socialist system within the 'divine order' of humankind could be no more than that. The primary enemy is none other than the

eternal Creator. And I have already despaired of socialism because humanity clearly does not want it.”⁵³

The topic of socialism would not surface again in Klee’s diaries and correspondence until 1919, after the fall of the short-lived communist Bavarian Council Republic.⁵⁴

Hausenstein and Klee met for the first time in April 1913. Klee invited the critic and his then wife, Marga, to a house concert of piano trios, featuring Klee on violin, his wife Lily on piano, and the virtuoso cellist Alexander Barjansky.⁵⁵ Although Klee had joined the Blaue Reiter group a little over a year before and had exhibited with other avant-garde artists in the *Moderne Bund* exhibition in Zurich, he had not yet received notice from any major critic, so the social contact with someone as prominent and prolific as Hausenstein must have seemed promising indeed.⁵⁶

The following summer Hausenstein included a brief mention of Klee in the long catalog essay he wrote for the Munich dealer Hans Goltz’s Neue Kunst gallery – it was his first general overview of recent art. He grouped Klee with those artists he saw to be engaged with “a new problem of modern art: the problem of the psychological.” He named Wassily Kandinsky, Gustav Klimt, Max Oppenheimer, Oskar Kokoschka, Ludwig Meidner, Marianne von Werefkin, and Alfred Kubin.⁵⁷ Such a motley grouping suggests how unformed Hausenstein’s view of current art must have been at the time. Yet he had made considerable progress by the end of the year, when he completed *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart*. Here he devoted almost a page to Klee, treating him exclusively as a graphic artist. Now Hausenstein emphasized Klee’s individuality within what he believed to be the coherent general tendency of “expressionism.”⁵⁸

He was a talent who “within a general modernity” was “personal to the point of eccentricity,” “the most extreme deformer” in the history of recent graphic art.⁵⁹ He had “achieved a style whose value lies wholly in its form, in its quirkily morbid handwriting.” His drawings were “the ultimate, psychological reflex of sensuous and, even more, suprasensuous experiences that were graphically realizable. [...] [T]he vision trembles in the air, like a half-formed thought that eludes definition. Out of this absolute vagueness, this objective vagueness, Klee makes something that as form is extraordinarily defined. We have similar feelings with Picasso; we have the feeling of a depravity sublime to the point of childishness, yet that carries not a moment with subject matter but directly and with the greatest intensity converts itself into artistic vision, knowing how to capture the vaguest experience with a calligraphy of unnamable but precise eroticism. Concepts like decadence are meaningless here: the intensity and incisiveness of form ultimately subdue any disorder, and in the end nothing remains but the firm impression of a music that is perfect in its way.”⁶⁰ This characterization, though acknowledging the eccentricity and potentially alienating effect of this art, was essentially positive, enthusiastically so. Understandably pleased, Klee wrote to Kubin: “I received Hausenstein’s book today. We come off well, we two. And it is nevertheless a completely normal book [...] and his cool reason will have a good effect for us.”⁶¹

The tension between Klee’s highly individualistic art and Hausenstein’s socialist ideal of a new collective style became evident in his second effort at writing on the artist. Within six months of completing *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart*, in which he had written only of Klee’s drawings, Hausenstein got his initial look at a selection of watercolors from the artist’s recent journey to Tunisia, exhibited in the

Fig. 9
 Paul Klee, *Blick zum Hafen von Hammamet*
 [View Towards the Harbour of Hammamet],
 1914, 35, watercolor on paper,
 21.5/21.7 x 27/26.6 cm, private collection
 Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern,
 Archive

inaugural exhibition of the Munich New Secession (FIG. 9).⁶² Now Klee the eccentric outlier had become even more so: the absolute solipsist, utterly detached from the world, living in “an isolation that completely transports him from any sense of locale. His exquisite watercolors from Africa are the music of one who has been liberated, who in marvelous confusion has entirely lost the connection to everything natural and concrete and solid local possibilities and now centers himself totally in the lonely spirituality of his life.”⁶³

Hausenstein refrained from passing judgment, but even a superficial acquaintance with his writing in these years reveals that such an art was profoundly at odds with his own values – Expressionism, after all, was supposedly “a product of an emerging sociability”;⁶⁴ art was “the highest form of social eroticism.”⁶⁵ Yet in Klee’s case it seems that Hausenstein, against his most deeply held convictions, had succumbed to a purely aesthetic eroticism. It’s jarring to read this review of the Munich New Secession alongside a short article by him that had appeared

only two months earlier, in which he made the case that the energies of a vital art must emanate from the people, from the general culture, even if the masses are themselves unconcerned with aesthetic issues. Art must have an “objective basis,” a *social* basis. “More and more we must unlearn our indulgence of the sensitive subjective-critical awareness of taste.”⁶⁶ The artistic form of the future would emerge from the growing drive for political organization, namely socialism.

Despite this obvious tension it appears that Hausenstein was content to live with this apparent contradiction, for at this time he evidently had plans to write more on Klee. In a letter from the end of the year, with the war now underway, Klee informed Hausenstein that *Deutsche Kunst und Dekoration*, the journal in which his review of the Munich New Secession had appeared, had requested “without obligation” a selection of his most recent works, presumably for possible publication. He asked Hausenstein to assist him in making the choice, allowing the critic to determine the “definitive selection” in accord

with “your special interests.” He then added: “Our venture is and remains audacious.”⁶⁷ Klee didn’t indicate what this bold venture was, but it seems clear that Hausenstein intended to engage further with his art, perhaps with a major article for the journal, or even a monograph. Whatever they had in mind nothing came of it at the time.

Four years would pass before Hausenstein again wrote on Klee.⁶⁸ For almost two years, from January 1916 to November 1917, he worked in the political division of the press office of the German Governor General in occupied Belgium.⁶⁹ In the meantime, in March 1916, Klee had been inducted into the reserves of the German army, and since January 1917 was serving as a clerk in the financial office of the Royal Bavarian Flying School in Gersthofen.⁷⁰ Hausenstein, returning to Munich in late 1917, joined the leading Munich daily *Münchner Neueste Nachrichten* as art critic. Learning this news in a letter from Lily, Klee was elated: “What a miracle!” he wrote to her.⁷¹ That this bode well for him was soon evident. Returning from a weekend leave in Munich to his military post, he purchased some newspapers while changing trains. He was delighted to find his work mentioned in a review by Hausenstein – the topic was the graphic exhibition of the Munich New Secession. Hausenstein was generally critical of the exhibition and much of the work in it; the major exceptions were two works by Kubin and “most of those by Klee” (there were thirty, a varied selection of drawings from the preceding decade), which left the strongest impression due to their “directness and vigor” (*das Stärkste an Unmittelbarkeit und Nachdruck*).⁷² But Hausenstein injected a huge qualifier: “This judgment is completely personal; it obligates no one. Especially with regard to my assessment of Klee I am aware that it neither can nor will offer a somehow universally valid norm of judgment; his

drawing is so subjective and so full of fundamentally problematic features that it is impossible to make a case for it on the basis of objective, general artistic criteria.”⁷³ Klee was nevertheless elated to have his work singled out for praise. He wrote to Lily that the “miracle that I would be appreciated there has occurred and remains a miracle in spite of the hedging.”⁷⁴ What he didn’t know was that four days before the review appeared he had received vastly more expansive and concrete praise from Hausenstein – praise simultaneously, paradoxically, undercut by the most severe reservations.

The occasion was a major lecture on Expressionism that Hausenstein presented in Berlin on March 14.⁷⁵ For most of it he reiterated his positions of *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart*. He devoted the largest part of his lecture to an attempt at establishing the parameters of Expressionism, identifying the ways in which it differed from *vorexpressionistische*, or pre-Expressionist art, a term he applied to the European art of the nineteenth century. The commonality linking these artistic expressions – he named, among others, Jacques-Louis David, Gustave Courbet, Édouard Manet, Auguste Rodin, Max Liebermann, and Adolf Hildebrand – in all their variety was a respect for the concrete object and the visual world as perceived.⁷⁶ Expressionism rejected this principle. Nature was subjected to brutal simplifications, distortions, and deformations in pursuit of a spiritual goal. “What the expressionist would like to paint, draw and chisel is the metaphysical, the trace of the divine in things. [...] And thus it approaches the religious. Once again the artist discovers Christian art and its motifs. God is again mentioned by name.”⁷⁷

Yet, his judgment sobered by the comparison of Expressionism with past art, Hausenstein now no longer believed it to constitute the art of the future. What was

to come, or what *should* come, what Hausenstein fervently *wanted* to come, was not more abstraction. He had now come to believe it was clear that naturalistic painting was not intrinsically any less “metaphysical” than abstract painting, and its greatest achievements were artistically superior. “The pendulum has completed its swing; what is positive in the future lies clearly in a new and reverent contentment with nature.”⁷⁸ What was needed was to “marvel anew at nature, [...] so unspeakably maligned, and to recall the sentence uttered by the supposedly passé Cezanne: ‘What is needed is to do Poussin over again after nature; that is all.’”⁷⁹

Klee’s art, it should be obvious, had no place in this revised program, and yet – he was the star of the lecture, the only artist Hausenstein discussed at length, and with the most lavish praise. He explicitly ranked this creator of works on the most intimate scale above Kandinsky and Picasso and, by implication, everyone else. Within his revised view of expressionism Klee now assumed a position of major importance. To be sure, Hausenstein still placed him at the outer extremes of the movement, as he had in 1914 – Ludwig Meidner, Oskar Kokoschka, and Emil Nolde were its most typical representatives; but Klee – no longer merely a draughtsman, yet still primarily a producer of *Blätter*, of works on paper rarely as large as twenty-five centimeters in either dimension – now became one of the pre-eminent masters of the formalist tendency within the movement: “In Expressionism [...] there was an effort to oppose to the representation of the object’s form the instantiation of the absolute pictorial means. This is the significance of the development from Matisse to Kandinsky, from Picasso to Klee. To a certain degree the painting and doctrine of Kandinsky are simply an attempt to counterpose [...] to the thing in it-

self [...] the emancipated medium, the medium in itself: absolute color as an autonomous element. Precisely this is realized on the basis of a more sublime talent by the painter and graphic artist Paul Klee. His drawings, stimulated by a slight motif, are an attempt to extract the charm, the profundity, the levity, the wit, the pathos, the terror of the pure graphic stroke and to capture the graphic means in all thinkable combinations at the peak of such abstraction – thereby to distill all possible formal properties of the graphic element. It is the sheerly incomparable significance of this artist that no one did this in such a personal and compelling manner as he – with the possible exception of Picasso, who, however (as a Latin with classical inclinations), scarcely possesses the musical profundity of Klee.”⁸⁰

Despite Klee’s cultivation of the graphic and painterly means in their purity, the significance of his art was not exhausted at that level. Hausenstein claimed, mistakenly, that the representation of objects remained fundamental to his art. Klee was apprehending the object at the instant “in which, through the effect of the hypermetropia of someone intensely gazing at it, it begins to disintegrate, the planar intersections [...] begin to dissolve and consequently the strangest molecular shifting occurs, and the strangest process of phosphorescence, of decay and reemergence seems to be consummated. Klee’s cubism is the representation of the momentary interval between two states of crystallization of the object.” Hausenstein went on to hail him as “the classic German representative of Cubism” (*der deutsche Klassiker des Kubismus*).⁸¹

Then, startlingly, after this effusive praise for Klee’s achievement Hausenstein revealed his profound misgivings about its implications: “Everything that Expressionism has produced is [...] consciously or unconsciously a bridge to the

metaphysical. One believed to be that much closer to the metaphysical the more abstractly one worked. Klee's art, agitating and then again charming like the Rococo, sensitive and benign like the Biedermeier, complicated and subject to irony, could certainly be an almost convincing example of the possibility of such an intention. But its subjectivity is so hard to fathom that at the same time it means the end of painting: nihilism in every direction. It is possible that the journey of art will lead there. That cannot be foreseen. We are also not speaking of that."⁸²

It was at this time that Hausenstein decided to write a book on Klee.

In his 1918 Munich New Secession review Hausenstein had expressed an interest in devoting "a special study to Klee's extremely trenchant style in an attempt to make it accessible to a wider audience (although never for a truly large one)."⁸³ He clearly acted on that thought soon thereafter, for in late May Klee wrote to him to discuss the illustrations.⁸⁴ This was several weeks before the publication of Hausenstein's Berlin lecture in *Die neue Rundschau*. It seems unlikely that at that time he would have shared with Klee the sentiments he had expressed there. We can only wonder what Klee thought when he read them – as he must have done after the lecture was published in July. We can infer this from a postcard he wrote to Lily shortly thereafter: "The Hausenstein essay, as flattering as it is for me, has nevertheless again provoked a kind of opposition within me, and I painted a rigorously organized piece, *Der Traum* (*The Dream*) (FIG. 10), one of my most compelling sheets, on coarse linen paper with a plaster ground [...]."⁸⁵ Interesting here is Klee's inclusion of the word "again" (*wieder*), which suggests that his uneasiness with Hausenstein's reading of his art was not new.⁸⁶

Shortly after the publication of his *Neue Rundschau* article Hausenstein ex-

panded it into a short book, which appeared in spring 1919 with the title *Über Expressionismus in der Malerei* (*On Expressionism in Painting*). In it he mitigated his judgment on Klee only somewhat, deleting the words "end of painting" and "nihilism" so that the passage now read: "its subjectivity [that is, of Klee's art] is so hard to fathom that it threatens to spell the end of the inalienable concept of an art public. It is possible that the journey of art will lead there. That cannot be foreseen." And here he added a sentence: "Moreover, it is not to be wished."⁸⁷ It is here that Hausenstein introduced the idea that Klee's art was "not of a public nature."

A strange episode later that year confirmed that Hausenstein meant what he said. The incident arose during a controversy, in 1919, over the unsuccessful campaign by the students of the Stuttgart Art Academy to have Klee succeed the retiring Adolf Hölzel as a professor at that institution.⁸⁸ Klee encouraged Oskar Schlemmer, then still a student and the leader of the initiative, to consult "Dr. Hausenstein [...] as an 'expert,' as funny as that may sound at first," for authoritative substantiation of his qualifications.⁸⁹ Whether Schlemmer followed through on this is not known, but the following November, as a decision was imminent, Hausenstein weighed in on the matter in *Münchner Neueste Nachrichten*. He had read of the controversy in the weekly *Kunstchronik*, in which the correspondent had questioned the appointment of Klee.⁹⁰ The text of Hausenstein's notice read, in part, as follows: "In the M[ünchner] N[eu]este N[ach]richten, Klee's art has repeatedly been considered with words of deep sympathy. That is all the more reason for the obligation to emphasize that the thought of appointing Klee to a position of this kind would be thoroughly misguided. It would be misguided because it fails to see that the most essential value

Fig. 10
Paul Klee, *Der Traum* [*The Dream*], 1918, 121,
watercolor and pen on primed linen on
paper, 20 x 25 cm, location unknown
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern,
Archive

of Klee, which lies in the absolute subjectivity and irrationality of his work (which is not only contrary to anything teachable but which also eludes nearly all explanation). Let us leave Klee in the only sphere in which one can imagine him: in the remoteness of his purely and unconstrainedly personal fantasy and in the secret enchanted world of his violin.”⁹¹

Hausenstein tipped off Klee in advance of the publication, feeling obliged to do so out of “loyalty,” sending him a carbon copy of his text.⁹² O. K. Werckmeister has remarked on the strangeness and seriousness of Hausenstein’s behavior – while writing a book on Klee! Now he aggressively intervened in Klee’s career, undermining his chances for a prestigious position and a regular income in a time of severe economic crisis.⁹³ Werckmeister takes Hausenstein’s statement at face value, but I find something partially specious, or at least not completely candid, in the critic’s reasoning. Hausenstein may have been consistent in stressing the difficulty of Klee’s art, its extreme “subjectivity,”

but let us recall he had also consistently lauded Klee’s formal mastery, his peerless cultivation of the pure plastic means – he would therefore have seemed among German artists an ideal successor to Hölzel, himself a pioneer in this regard.⁹⁴ But in Hausenstein’s notice on that controversy, the “classic German representative of Cubism” seemed forgotten, stressing as it did the artist’s subjective remoteness, suggesting that the principles of Klee’s art were totally idiosyncratic, even mystical in origin. Viewed in the context of Hausenstein’s growing disenchantment with the avant-garde, it is probable that his objections to Klee’s appointment must have had less to do with the “unteachability” of his principles (certainly Klee’s later lectures at the Bauhaus would prove that assertion unfounded) than with Hausenstein’s fears about the dissemination of Klee’s artistic viewpoint. In a position where he could exert direct influence on future generations of artists, Klee could further an artistic tendency that Hausenstein regarded as highly un-

desirable. And yet in that same month he had signed a contract with Kurt Wolff Verlag to produce a book that, inevitably, would promote the artist who was its subject.⁹⁵ It must have been confusing for Klee. Yet he seemingly harbored no resentment toward Hausenstein on account of his intervention. Perhaps as an olive branch he invited the Hausensteins to a musical evening.⁹⁶ But even if he was sanguine about being rejected for the position at the Stuttgart Academy he could hardly have been happy with Hausenstein's characterization of his art.

Über Expressionismus in der Malerei was extraordinarily successful. It had already gone into its fifth printing when Hausenstein published a new essay, "Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick" (Art at this moment), in which he shed what remaining illusions he had about "expressionism."⁹⁷ The art he had hailed in 1914 as a "catastrophe" for naturalism was itself, he now declared, a "catastrophe": "Expressionism is dead. [...] The category no longer says anything." "We who have consciously experienced, who have loved Expressionism, [...] today live with the consuming feeling of having arrived *vis-à-vis de rien*."⁹⁸ In *Über Expressionismus in der Malerei* he had declared it to be coming to an end, but still held that it had been a coherent tendency. Now he no longer believed that, he saw no unifying factor; "One could just as well maintain that no one is an Expressionist as claim that all are, or a few: because it is not certain what Expressionism is." There was an "immeasurable span between Picasso and Nolde, Kandinsky and Rousseau, Klee and Meidner, Seewald and Kokoschka. The common denominator vanishes."⁹⁹ "There is no Expressionism. There is Alexandria. There is the Hellenism of the twentieth century."¹⁰⁰ In reality Expressionism had been not the precursor of a new culture, it was a symptom of the disintegration of culture itself. In-

deed, the very survival of art itself now seemed threatened. For Hausenstein the *Gegenstandslosigkeit*, the "objectlessness" that was a feature of some expressionist art was no accident. It was now not merely God who had no firmly delineated presence in human consciousness, but *things themselves*. With abstraction "[t]he thing disappeared from painting as it disappeared from the world," a consequence of the absence of any compelling metaphysical belief.¹⁰¹ One cannot, he argued, blame the artists; they have only painted their time.¹⁰²

Between the completion of *Über Expressionismus in der Malerei* and the appearance of "Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick" a book appeared that apparently intensified the pessimistic turn in Hausenstein's thinking: the first volume of Oswald Spengler's *Der Untergang des Abendlandes (The Decline of the West)*.¹⁰³ It had appeared in 1918, and was widely reviewed in the cultural press. Wilhelm Worringer, who before the war had, like Hausenstein, prophesied that Expressionism was the harbinger of an anonymous, collective style, now declared that all that was needed was for sinister words like "decline of the west" to be uttered and "all at once one saw the expressionists from the rear [...] and suddenly it looked like a last-minute panic of an art that had despaired of itself."¹⁰⁴ Spengler displaced the optimistic dialectical model of historical development that Hausenstein embraced and revived the biological paradigm, which had dominated art history from Vasari until it was supplanted by Hegel's teleological paradigm.¹⁰⁵ "*Cultures are organisms*," he wrote; "Cultural history is their biography [original emphasis]."¹⁰⁶ Each culture was a unique unrepeatable phenomenon; once it died its spirit never returned. The youth of Christian culture had been the Ottonian, the Romanesque, and the Gothic; its maturity was the Baroque (broadly defined to em-

brace Michelangelo, Rembrandt, Shakespeare, and Bach). With the Rococo came autumn and the Enlightenment marked the beginning of decay.¹⁰⁷ Spengler had particularly harsh things to say about modern painting, an art form that in his view no longer had any reason to exist. Manet's art, he declared, had marked the end of painting as a significant art. "From that follows – a bitter admission – that visual art is at an end. The crisis of the nineteenth century was the death struggle. [...] What today is practiced as art is impotent and a lie, music after Wagner as well as painting after Manet, Cézanne, Leibl, and Menzel."¹⁰⁸ In the context of Spengler's text the significance of Hausenstein's comparison of contemporary artistic culture to Alexandria becomes clear, for Spengler had made precisely this point: "We need only to place ourselves in the Alexandria of 200 B.C. in order to acquaint ourselves with the artistic noise with which a cosmopolitan civilization knows how to deceive itself about the death of its art. There, like today in the world capitals of Europe, a chase after the illusion of artistic progress, [...] of a 'new style,' of 'undreamed of possibilities,' a theoretical babble."¹⁰⁹ Spengler's book was to have a decisive impact on Hausenstein's concept for his Klee monograph.

In November 1919, upon signing a contract for his planned monograph, Hausenstein conveyed the news to Klee, relating his concept for the book: "I want to write it before the year is out: it is inwardly prepared and actually needs only to be produced. But in any case I would like as soon as possible to study your entire oeuvre with you: for the selection of pictures and to clarify some thoughts that are perhaps not quite clear to me. You are placed at the center and around this center the problem of the art of our time (and

of our time in general) is developed. The book will perhaps become half-novel."¹¹⁰

Two drafts for *Kairuan* give us a sense of Hausenstein's early concept for the book.¹¹¹ One consists of seven pages in his own hand in *Kurrentschrift*, the German cursive script – I have designated it "Draft A." It appears to be the earlier of the two; its text is subdivided as chapters one, two, and three, although their contents do not correspond to those chapters in the published book. The second draft, which I am calling "Draft B," consists of twenty-one pages (albeit roughly the same number of words as Draft A), apparently dictated by Hausenstein to his Belgian wife, Margot, whom he had married in May 1919 and to whom he would dedicate the book.¹¹² Here the content prefigures that of *Kairuan*'s opening chapters, and for that reason I take it to represent a later stage of Hausenstein's thinking.

In this draft for the early chapters, Hausenstein relates that he found Klee's art "disturbing to the highest degree," the artist "aloof, undiscoverable."¹¹³ Yet despite his misgivings and seemingly against his will, he writes that he came strongly under the spell of these pictures: "The things haunt me. My thoughts during walks take on their colors and their lines. I can't think through my own thoughts. Klee interferes, that is to say his colors and his lines do. If I am listening to music a watercolor by him pushes its way in. Gray walls in the street become hallucinations with his colors and his lines. The inscriptions of children become dangerous. [...] It's becoming an obsession with me, Hoffmannesque. I must free myself. I am inventing the fairy tale of the evolutionary history of art. [...] The line from the visible thing to nothingness; to a mere medium that plays with itself. But is it a nothingness? Oh! No. It is only a world reflecting on its innermost self. Since there are no longer any objects out there and no belief within, nothing remains but to paint

one's inner reflexes. Nerves. Perhaps that is a naturalism turned inward rather than outward."¹¹⁴

Drafting his "fairy tale," Hausenstein may have concocted a Hoffmannesque fantasy in the books opening chapters, but the contents of "Draft A" show him to be earnestly seeking to understand Klee's art in the context of art history and contemporary art. When he proposes to write "the fairy tale of the evolutionary history of art," he is writing as someone who was well positioned to do so with respect to Western European art: he had previously produced books on Pieter Bruegel the Elder, French Rococo, the Baroque, and Grünewald's *Isenheim Altar*, modern European art of the previous half-century, and the 664-page survey of the nude figure in Western art from the Stone Age to modern times in *Der nackte Mensch*. And he concludes that Klee doesn't really fit anywhere:¹¹⁵ "The style of this art has nothing in common with antiquity, Rome, Renaissance. Hardly anything with the Gothic or the Baroque either. The lingering impressionistic trace is not decisive. Rather the style has a distant as well as unconscious commonality with primitive drawings: with the ductus of pre-historic engravings on reindeer antlers, on mammoth teeth; with early Christian signets; with the pentagrams of magians with the signs of the Kabbalists; with the notches [...] on runic staffs. Still this doesn't explain the origin of this extremely personal style. [...] The origin lies precisely in the unerringness of the person, in the interdiction of all influences; in his shutting out tradition and community; in the completeness of his isolation."¹¹⁶

Elsewhere in *Kairuan*, Hausenstein writes of Klee's art: "Incapable of orienting itself within tradition, there arose once more an art of a magian nature."¹¹⁷ What did he mean?

When, in the spring of 1918, he decided to write a book on Klee, Hausenstein

asked him for an autobiographical summary of his life and career.¹¹⁸ Klee promised to send it soon, yet didn't provide it until a year and a half later, in December 1919.¹¹⁹ It took the form of a chronology totaling roughly 4000 words. On the first page, describing his origins, he wrote of the musical training of his parents, adding that his mother was "half Swiss (Basel). Her remaining ancestry is not completely clarified, by way of southern France, it can be oriental."¹²⁰ It is tempting to conclude that this single brief remark may have been the catalyst for Hausenstein's concept for *Kairuan*; in which Klee is fancifully, fantastically orientalized. Hausenstein had not previously suggested any such connection. In the draft for the early chapters he wrote, after describing the ambience of the Klees' Schwabing apartment: "A distant horizon becomes visible. A world of big cats and workers on the coast of North Africa, who weave colorful mats while thinking of Allah and of nothing. So one asks, have you Arab blood? Various threads link his mother to Africa."¹²¹ Assuming this exchange occurred, Hausenstein doesn't report Klee's response. In Draft A he writes of Klee's relationship to the exotic, specifically to the Arabic: "An exotic association is in play, giving the script and painting certain exotic ambiguities. Moreover we don't have *exact* information about his blood. Is he an Arab or not? If he isn't there is admittedly an *elective affinity*. Then he paints as *though he were* an Oriental [original emphasis]."¹²²

In *Kairuan* Hausenstein went all in on this orientalizing of Klee – seven of the book's sixteen chapters contain passages connecting him with Arab ethnicity or culture. In the fourth chapter, the first in which Klee is discussed at length, Hausenstein describes him as *der Fremd-artige*, the strange, exotic one: "This person is not from here"; his pallor is "the brown of an Arab man bleached in a

northern cellar.”¹²³ He imagines him in Arab garb, “wrapped in a white burnoose, the countenance framed and shaded by a white cloth. [...] [S]et him on a white stallion with rosy red chaps or between the humps of a camel. Open the seldom trod paths before the Atlas Mountains, the dunes of the desert – and see, he will be at home there: [...] comfortable with the damascened saber.”¹²⁴ It is thus “no coincidence that the son of the beautiful Basel mother with the mysterious background can tell of an African journey. It was not just any beautiful journey to the edge of the black continent. Rather it was the passage of the person to himself. It had to be, for he needed it in order to understand himself.”¹²⁵

At this point in his narrative Hausenstein now proceeded to orientalize Klee’s art. Looking over his works, “covered with wondrous signs that don’t relate to any of our habits of judgment,” one “suddenly senses a connection that explains much. Bewitched by this Arabian skull [i.e., Klee’s], the viewer wants nothing but arabesques: bands of color that intermingle; ambiguity that can assume form only in ornament – since those faithful to the Prophet avoid the depiction of the human form, indeed of things, and they content themselves with the rhythm of decorations, accustomed to record in them the deep meaning of life.”¹²⁶ Here is another instance of Hausenstein seeing what he wanted to see. Klee wrote nothing about the absence of figuration in Islamic art, which in any case, is not universally true of this tradition – as a recent controversy in the United States has reminded us, it is not even universally true with respect to images of the Prophet.¹²⁷ Moreover, Klee acquired four *figurative* watercolors in Kairouan by anonymous amateur Tunisian artists. Three were architectural fantasies, the fourth showed the twelfth-century Sufi mystic, Sidi Abd al-Qādir al-Jīlānī, taming wild animals.

Given his interest in the Tunisian journey, one wonders whether Hausenstein may even have seen these works in Klee’s collection and, for the sake of his thesis, simply chosen to ignore them.¹²⁸

In his Klee commentaries from 1918–1920, Hausenstein may have stressed Klee’s eccentricity, yet he situated and discussed him within the parameters of European modernism. Now Klee stands apart, alone. What’s behind this new orientalizing take on Klee? The story of Klee’s mother’s possible North African ancestry seems hardly sufficient to explain it.

I suspect Spengler was the catalyst. At the beginning of “Draft A” Hausenstein wrote: “Starting from ‘Decline of the West.’ No objects, no persons.”¹²⁹ While *Decline of the West* dealt a blow to his idealistic belief in Expressionism, it also offered Hausenstein a new framework for theorizing Klee outside the traditions and current moment of European art. What Hausenstein writes here of Klee’s art corresponds to Spengler’s characterization of the *magische Seele der arabischen Kultur*, the magian soul of Arab culture.¹³⁰ He describes the forms of magian arts as characterized by “their dissolution into the incorporeal, aniconic arabesque.” The arabesque signified “a tremendous devaluation of the real, to which it denies an intrinsic meaning [...]”¹³¹ “Since the magian feeling for the world knows not the logic of the real, [...] expression is ultimately reduced to the arabesque, to Saracenic ornament.”¹³² There are several references in *Kairouan* to Klee as *Magier*, a magus, and his art as *magisch*.¹³³

Klee did identify his Tunisian sojourn with a crucial moment in his development as a painter – his spontaneous intuitive grasp of color. In April 1914 he had travelled to Tunisia with his fellow painters August Macke and Louis Moilliet.¹³⁴ They visited Tunis, the nearby coastal town of St. Germain (today Ezzahra), Hammamet,

and Kairouan.¹³⁵ Up to this point Klee had felt tentative as a colorist, and at Kairouan, after a week of painting water-colors drenched with the splendors of North African light and color, he experienced an epiphany: “I now abandon work. [...] Color possesses me. I need not strain for it. It has me forever, I know that. That is the meaning of this happy hour: color and I are one, I am a painter.”¹³⁶ Klee did savor the exoticism of Tunisian culture – at one point he described an Arab wedding he witnessed as “thousand and one nights as an extract with 99% reality content.”¹³⁷ But there is no trace of the sentiments Hausenstein claims that Klee experienced there.

Klee’s diary for his Tunisian journey, it must be noted, is a later redaction – the original has not survived, evidently destroyed by Klee himself.¹³⁸ Michael Baumgartner writes that Klee didn’t complete the redaction before autumn of 1921, which means it was done after he had read Hausenstein’s monograph, which he reported doing in a letter to the author the previous January.¹³⁹ In its present form most of the Tunisian diary reads like a simple transcription of the day-to-day activities of the group, with interpolations of a retrospective nature – the famous passage “color and I are one” seems such a case. Baumgartner plausibly suggests that in the redacted diary Klee was pushing back against Hausenstein’s orientaling reading.¹⁴⁰

Hausenstein, it should be clear, had his own agenda, and it was not Klee’s – in fact he hardly discusses what Klee actually produced in Tunisia. “From the point of view of the art historian,” he comments of the journey, “not much more can be established than a consolidation of Klee’s sense of color.”¹⁴¹ Indeed, Hausenstein, who had acquired a Tunisian watercolor for himself, chose not to illustrate any in *Kairuan*.¹⁴² For him much, much more was at stake than a mastery of color:

“Kairouan. The name became the symbol for a many-sided experience.” Above all Kairouan signified Africa, the Islamic “Orient,” and a culture with a radically different relationship to the physical world. Kairouan meant “to recognize, or find confirmed, that things are indeed without substance; that they should be despised as mere appearance.”¹⁴³ The disappearance of “things” in the present historical moment, the idea Hausenstein had recently introduced in “Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick,” is one of *Kairuan*’s overarching themes. Two years before, he had claimed that expressionist artists sought to paint “the metaphysics of things.”¹⁴⁴ Now, in his despair, he asserts that in Europe there are no longer things. Objects, things, have, to be sure, not actually disappeared, they have merely “withdrawn from our wandering eye.”¹⁴⁵ Our gaze has become scattered, unfocused, so that we are incapable of perceiving the “effect of the divine mystery.”¹⁴⁶

Hausenstein develops this theme in his fourteenth chapter, “Das Nichts,” or nothingness, the bleakest in the book, the blackest expression of despair. Here he describes the hollowiness of the present, the consequence of a moral hollowiness. “The categories of thing and person have become extinct.” Today they “exist only in their own ruins.”¹⁴⁷ All that remains are “scattered shreds of the object world; remnants of a concrete reality smashed to pieces by the express train or the automobile, chopped, flattened and bleached of color by the cinematograph.” Klee, alone among artists, sees this world as it is. In this sense he is not an abstract artist but a “naturalist.”¹⁴⁸

To understand the significance of Hausenstein’s remarks on the disappearance of things it is helpful to go back to 1913 and his long, fundamental article on a sociology of visual art, which could be read as a kind of prolegomenon to *Der nackte Mensch*, which appeared later that

year.¹⁴⁹ In it he offered a theory, threaded with many concrete historical examples, of a social history of art that he defined in terms of the changing relationship of human beings to the physical things (*die Dinge*) of the world, a relationship determined by the mode of social and economic organization. Hausenstein explained his choice of the nude human figure as an index of this history, not as subject matter, but as artistic form. He treated these motifs as universal, “the forms of elemental human existence.”¹⁵⁰ In *Der nackte Mensch* Hausenstein looked at pre-historic art, the Egyptians, ancient near Eastern art, the ancient Greeks, and so on, right up to the early twentieth century. Among the world’s great artistic traditions there is one conspicuous omission: the art of Islam. Hausenstein does mention it briefly over two pages, citing Quranic and Sunni texts proscribing the representation of the human form.¹⁵¹ It was in Tunisia, Hausenstein claims in *Kairuan*, that Klee experienced a tradition in which the absence of things has a positive religious value. It is an artistic tradition that privileges abstraction, the “arabesque,” over representation.

But Klee’s encounter with his alleged Arab roots did not solve the artistic problem as Hausenstein saw it: how does one visually represent nothingness? It seemed an impossible task. And yet, he proposes, Klee achieves it, paradoxically, miraculously, with the “ultimate precision.”¹⁵² His solution has nothing to do with the long, exhausted tradition of Western art, not even with Picasso and Cubism. But Klee does find a model in tradition – in the tradition of Western music. “It is the miracle of music that it originates out of nothing.”¹⁵³ It has order, form, and structure without any dependence on things. Klee’s model is not contemporary program music, with its representationalism,¹⁵⁴ but the “absolute configuration” of the music of the past. The

music of the classical period “gives to stylus and brush the genius [...] of order in itself;” that of the Romantic composers a sense for “splendor, color, abundance, for the picturesque, for the rhetoric of the volute, for polyphony.” This link with tradition, a “productive conservatism,” is a means of “self-preservation” for an art not grounded in objects; it gives it “stability” and “equilibrium.”¹⁵⁵

So much for music; what then of painting? If things are no longer the objects of art, he writes, then the arts reciprocally become their objects.¹⁵⁶ There is an “infiltration” of the visual by the musical. Music does not merely provide Klee with form and structure, but also becomes an object. Klee translates acoustic structures into visual ones. Yet his art remains connected to painting through his treatment of the medium itself. His works are “made like painting, drawn like drawing” (*gemacht wie Malerei, gezeichnet wie Zeichnung*). After the removal of the object, “look at what is left. [...] [T]his is what they call form. An objection is imminent – one anticipates it: form has to realize, to represent something. Of course it does. Here it realizes itself. [...] In a world from which objects have been lost it has become its own object. [...] Form paints itself. Drawing draws itself. The medium emancipates itself, as the serf once did. [...] Yesterday’s form has become the object of form today.”¹⁵⁷

Throughout *Kairuan* Hausenstein refers to Klee as *der Malerzeichner*, the painter-draughtsman – he uses the term forty-seven times.¹⁵⁸ It is a fitting neologism for an artist whose favored support was paper rather than the canvas or panel, whose most characteristic works treat line and color as mutually distinct elements. But it also probably has to do with Hausenstein’s view of the fragmentation of modernity, a shattered world. “Today, the painter who is consistent must make drawings,” he writes; “for there is

no longer anything to support the breadth of the painterly, although the situation spurs the speculation of graphic art.”¹⁵⁹ Painting demanded a holistic apprehension of the visual world, of things. Given their ostensible disappearance, Klee, true to his time, could represent only the elements of the pictorial medium, line and color, form representing itself; they cannot fuse into the fullness of an image of the natural world.

To grasp the significance of Hausenstein’s remarks here, one must read the book he completed immediately before *Kairuan, Vom Geist des Barock*, which he presented to Klee as a gift at the end of 1919.¹⁶⁰ For Hausenstein the Baroque becomes an ideal, a countermodel to the fragmented modernity that had produced Expressionism, with which he had by now become so disillusioned.¹⁶¹ He had previously published the final chapter, virtually identical to how it would appear in the book, in the July 1919 issue of *Der neue Merkur* under the title, “Wir und das Barock” (We and the Baroque); in the book it was titled “Das Ganze,” the whole.¹⁶² The Baroque was “the painterly style par excellence.”¹⁶³ Moreover, this painterliness was pervasive in all visual art forms of the period, not only in painting but in sculpture and architecture. Hausenstein exclaims joyously, enviously: “Baroque is a style: it devours life. A style!”¹⁶⁴ This painterly style embraced nature in all its sensuality; its distinctive features were not made, they were “ejaculated.”¹⁶⁵ The painterly was integrally identified with the organic, with the naturalistic, in all of which Hausenstein drew a contrast with the abstract, constructed, anti-painterly, anti-naturalistic expressionist artwork.¹⁶⁶ This pervasive painterly style was “a spasm of the boundless baroque collectivity.”¹⁶⁷

Hausenstein’s observation on the pervasiveness of painterliness in all art forms recalls Wölfflin’s *Kunst-*

geschichtliche Grundbegriffe (Principles of Art History), which he had reviewed in 1916. Indeed, Wölfflin’s book may have been the catalyst for Hausenstein’s subsequent exuberant panegyric on the Baroque. He was clearly taken with the author’s theory of the cyclical nature of art’s historical development, of alternating linear and painterly epochs. He found therein a lesson for the present: despite the book’s “reserved neutrality” it was “movingly modern. [...] The poles of art history have been proved; the world is leaping from the classical to the Baroque – from yesterday to today.”¹⁶⁸ In *Vom Geist des Barock* Hausenstein claimed to see in Lovis Corinth and Max Slevogt, painters of an earlier generation, an historical advance guard of a newly emerging moment of Baroque painterliness. “A more recent name can be added to these two, the name Kokoschka. To move in the sphere of the Baroque is not a coincidental art-historical hobby. The Baroque is the style to which, historically and objectively, we are perhaps most closely disposed.”¹⁶⁹ Then, in “Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick,” he took up this idea and developed it: “Kokoschka has abandoned neither the painterly nor nature. Moreover: because a meaningful art is total his art encompasses an original metaphysics, which doesn’t so much rehabilitate the metaphysical element in the gothic and the baroque as supplant, replace, or if you will, newly identify it. Kokoschka is important: he contains the whole (*das Ganze*). He is a sign of the unvarying greatness that is called art. Finally: unvarying greatness also has a future dimension. Kokoschka is the future. Therefore: painting, nature and metaphysics are the future. What Kokoschka signifies: Art shall be – insofar as it exists at all. It shall paint. It shall have nature.”¹⁷⁰

Hausenstein never wrote so rapturously about Kokoschka elsewhere. In the

second edition of *Die Kunst des 20. Jahrhunderts* he praised the Austrian for the presence of “elements of a strong painterly culture” in his art.¹⁷¹ Kokoschka had remained within tradition, and had proved that Expressionism was possible without the abandonment of the “richness of developed painterly means.”¹⁷² And as in *Vom Geist des Barock*, Hausenstein identified painterliness with wholeness, *das Ganze*, encompassing religion and a devotion to God’s creation.¹⁷³

Hausenstein published “Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick” in book form later in 1920, as he was completing the text of *Kairuan*.¹⁷⁴ There he made minor changes in the original article and added an extended conclusion. One of the changes to the original text is noteworthy for his positioning of Klee in the current art scene. In describing the “immeasurable span” between “expressionist” artists he now reduced the four pairings in the article (Picasso and Nolde, Kandinsky and Rousseau, Klee and Meidner, Seewald and Kokoschka) to two, altering the combinations. Now the passage read: “between Picasso and Rousseau, Klee and Kokoschka.”¹⁷⁵ When one considers the chronological proximity of the book to the writing of *Kairuan*, this passage in the latter becomes striking: “Where are we? We know this: Klee is the art of the historical moment, in which things no longer reside simply within their boundaries nor in their former relations [...]. [T]his is the art of the historical moment, in which things have vacated the realm of physics, of sensuous proportion, of simple spiritual relations in order to pass over into the realm of the metaphysical – which however did not yet find centralization and articulation in a dogma. In the heady whiff of transition things have not yet arrived at the new, blissful certainty.”¹⁷⁶ So Klee’s art was the art of the current historical moment, but even now it was being superseded by the art of Kokoschka, ostensibly the art of the

future, in which things would again have physical substance, representing a new metaphysics, a new dogma, a return to nature, the “breadth of the painterly” and “the whole.”

In the final pages of *Kairuan* Hausenstein makes an interesting move. The spiritual upheaval and disorientation of the present time suggest a historical parallel – the era of the Reformation, that of Grünewald, Bosch, and Bruegel.¹⁷⁷ The stimulus for this idea was undoubtedly Grünewald’s *Isenheim Altar*. In 1917, to protect it from the ravages of war, the altar had been removed from Colmar to the Alte Pinakothek in Munich, where it went on view on November 24, 1918, two weeks after Germany’s surrender, remaining exhibited until September 27, 1919.¹⁷⁸ Hausenstein published a monograph on it in 1919, just as he was beginning to work on *Kairuan*.¹⁷⁹ It’s clear he believed there was a parallel between Grünewald’s turbulent era and the present. In *Der Isenheimer Altar des Matthias Grünewald* he wrote of the period: “The ring of the old theology is shattering. Reformation is being prepared. While Grünewald is painting the *Isenheim Altar*, new insights are forming in Luther and others. [...] The unquestioned calm of the old dogma has vanished.”¹⁸⁰ And in *Kairuan*: “It seems as if the phenomenon were cyclic. Klee: the name grows beyond the personal into a symptom of the time, marking the return of the moment when the old dogma and stable things were lost, and when the enigmatic appears in anticipation of the new dogma, perhaps of the new reality.”¹⁸¹

In the book’s final chapter Hausenstein reproduced Klee’s recent watercolor, *Angelus Novus* (FIG. 11). He must surely have recognized in the figure of Klee’s new angel a parody of Grünewald’s resurrected Christ from the *Isenheim Altar* (FIG. 12).¹⁸² Although the direction of the legs is reversed, the upraised arms and frontal pose echo Grünewald’s Christ fig-

Fig. 11
Paul Klee, *Angelus Novus*, 1920, 32, oil transfer drawing and watercolor on paper mounted on an engraving after a portrait of Martin Luther by Lukas Cranach, on paperboard, 31.8 × 24.2 cm, The Israel Museum, Jerusalem, gift of Fania and Gershom Scholem, Jerusalem; John Herring, Marlene and Paul Herring, Jo Carole and Ronald Lauder, New York
Photo credit: HIP / Art Resource, NY

Fig. 12
Matthias Grünewald, *Isenheim Altarpiece*, detail of *The Resurrection* (outer wing panel), 1513, 2.49 × 0.92 m, Musée d'Unterlinden, Colmar, France
© Musée d'Unterlinden, Dist. RMN-Grand Palais / Art Resource, NY

ure. As was usually his practice throughout the book Hausenstein doesn't refer to the work by title, but directly opposite the full-page plate we read: "There are also a few painters, to whom things (*die Dinge*) have already been restored. [...] They believe in the Creator – believe in Him with a catechetical rigor, similar to the artists of the Baroque or the Nazarenes, in the midst of suppression of the object and the human in this age. With that the world is *again resurrected* for them (*wieder auf-erstanden*), yet so new as the old world, after Christ, was the same and still a new one, with new energies for well nigh two thousand years. [...] The object, immortal in spite of everything, [...] perhaps began to become visible again to the eye as it turned homeward [my emphasis]."¹⁸³ Hausenstein may have found this figure of a new angel, a divine messenger, one moreover recalling Grünewald's resurrected Christ, a fitting one to juxtapose to his remarks on the hoped-for resurrec-

tion of painting that would again embrace nature, the world of things, and God.

But who were these "few painters"? Hausenstein doesn't name them here, but it's certain Paul Klee was not one of them.¹⁸⁴ We know from his books on the *Isenheim Altarpiece*, the Baroque, and *Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick*, all published while he was at work on *Kairuan*, that Hausenstein believed it was Kokoschka who pointed to the art of the future.¹⁸⁵ Hausenstein goes on to write in the book's final pages: "In order to paint things – visible, simple, and shared – the artist today would need only this certainty: that they are nature, nature once more and nevertheless and ultimately creatures of God. [...] A certainty that seems to be within sight. The painter-draughtsman Klee is the image of the moment that must precede such certainty. His activity stands between the history of the things of yesterday, the emptiness of those of today, and the longed for, not yet clasped fullness of the things of tomorrow. His painting and drawing are the psychological moment between these conditions.

Fig. 13
Paul Klee, *Angelus Novus*, 1920, 32, detail
Photo: R. H. Quaytman

Fig. 14
Friedrich Müller, *Dr. Martin Luther*, 1838,
engraving, 33.4 × 27.2 cm [plate], Collection
R. H. Quaytman

We are grateful to this maligned man, who endured martyrdom, for awareness of our situation and much of the quest for salvation.”¹⁸⁶

For Hausenstein, then, Klee was a transitional figure. *Angelus Novus*, with its title and its evocation of Grünewald’s *Resurrection*, must have seemed to him a fitting image for this moment in his text, with its expression of hope for the future of painting. But this abstract, schematic, parodic figure by the *Malerzeichner* certainly did not represent the art Hausenstein was yearning for, Klee’s art did not

fulfill that hope. Rather it exemplified “the most radical sign of the contemporary state of mind, which, a stranger to the churches, is yet of a pious heart; which encounters things with mistrust because they are nothing by themselves; one which however knows not enough of nature yet not so much of God that it could have the confidence to paint things.”¹⁸⁷

But in what spirit did Klee create this work? Heinz Brüggemann, one of the first scholars to note the resemblance of the pose to Grünewald’s resurrected Christ, asked whether it was “unthinkable to read Klee’s New Angel as a [...] deforming, disfiguring, at once destructive and constructive grappling with Grünewald’s *Resurrection*.”¹⁸⁸

A recent discovery about *Angelus Novus* may, I believe, add a further dimension to the import of Klee’s watercolor. In 2015 the artist R. H. Quaytman, while preparing a suite of works inspired by *Angelus Novus*, made a remarkable find, hiding in plain sight as it were, but not discernible in most reproductions. Examining Klee’s watercolor in the Israel Museum in Jerusalem, she discovered it to be mounted over what appeared to be a sixteenth-century engraving, visible around the periphery of the watercolor – a fact never before registered by commentators. In the lower-left corner was the monogram of the interlocked letters LC, and in a script of the era the date of 152_, the final digit partially obscured by the edge of Klee’s sheet (FIG. 13).¹⁸⁹ After scouring through thousands of images on the internet Quaytman identified the print: It was not a work of the 1520s but an engraving of Martin Luther, made in 1838 by the German artist Friedrich Müller (FIG. 14). This discovery generated excitement as well as puzzlement. Why would Klee mount a watercolor onto an engraving, and over one of Martin Luther, an image that, moreover, no one but he could see?¹⁹⁰

In her recent monograph on *Angelus Novus* Annie Bourneuf has thoroughly recounted the circumstances of this discovery and, in a richly detailed discussion of the works historical context, interrogated its possible significance for our understanding of Klee's watercolor. Building on Quaytman's find, she asks: "Did Klee want anyone to see this 'Easter egg'? Is it a private joke?"¹⁹¹ She refers to it as "Klee's little age-spotted caricature of Grünewald's Christ."¹⁹² She comments further: "If Klee's angel mimics Grünewald's Christ, he seems to do so rather mockingly, rendering the blinding radiance of the halo around Jesus's head as the oversized noggin of a caricature." She interprets it as an "ambivalent icon, [...] both enacting and deflating hopes such as [Franz] Marc's or Hausenstein's of a turning point ahead."¹⁹³ I believe it's possible to be more specific.

I think it likely that *Angelus Novus* was indeed a private joke of sorts, an *ad hominem* gesture from Klee to Hausenstein.¹⁹⁴ This scenario appears more plausible when we learn that Hausenstein had given Klee a copy of his *Der Isenheimer Altar* at Christmas 1919, and that in acknowledging the gift Klee reported reading the book with "the greatest interest. For all its richness it sticks to the facts."¹⁹⁵ But what must he have thought of this passage, by the author of a forthcoming monograph on him? "Grünewald possessed the power to bind expression once more within the contours of organic appearance. [...] Today such a legacy lives on in the best pictures of Kokoschka. The model stands before us. Grünewald represents the art, the sense of responsibility, of raising expression above the personal and making of it an image grounded in the object, beyond subjectivity. It is here that Grünewald's importance for the whole of the new painting begins."¹⁹⁶ Let us recall that Hausenstein had consistently stressed, right up through *Kairuan*,

that Klee's art was distinguished by its "absolute subjectivity."¹⁹⁷

I believe these circumstances give added resonance, added punch to *Angelus Novus*. Might Klee's new angel be his mischievous counterproposal for the "new painting"? An anti-naturalistic, decidedly unpainterly work by the *Malerzeichner*, irreverently mocking the motif of Grünewald's resurrection, physically canceling a metonymic image of the Reformation, to which Hausenstein looked back as analogous to the present moment? A newly born puckish angel with fledgling wings and birdlike feet, suddenly irrupts on a sheet stained with simulated foxing, casting its eyes sideward as if to orient itself in these first moments of its existence.¹⁹⁸ Reading Hausenstein's two recent books Klee may well have grown impatient with his lugubrious nostalgia for past art, his longing for a return to nature and God as the path for the "new painting."¹⁹⁹ Pushing back, the sheet seems to declare: *this*, lieber Herr Doctor, is the "new painting!"²⁰⁰

The Klee/Hausenstein nexus seems to me the most plausible explanation for the inclusion of the Luther engraving – perhaps a playful but private allusion known only to the two men. Hausenstein wrote to Klee, asking to meet in his Goltz retrospective to determine the choice of illustrations for the book.²⁰¹ (As it turned out, twenty-two of *Kairuan's* twenty-six full-page plates were in the exhibition, including *Angelus Novus*, which was reproduced without its border.) In viewing the exhibition with Klee Hausenstein might well have noticed the border formed by the underlying print, with its *faux* Cranach monogram and date, and might have asked him about it. In any case, it appears that the choice of reproductions for *Kairuan* was a joint undertaking. Klee's "new angel," superimposed over an image of Luther with a date from the time of the Reformation, seems like a physical

Fig. 15
Paul Klee, *Das Lamm* [*The Lamb*], 1920, 39,
oil and pen on cardboard,
31.2/31.5 x 40.7 cm, Städel Museum,
Frankfurt am Main

Fig. 16
Matthias Grünewald. *Crucifixion*, panel from
Isenheim Altarpiece, detail, 1513, oil on
limewood panel, Musée d'Unterlinden,
Colmar, France
Photo credit: Erich Lessing / Art Resource,
NY

exemplification of Hausenstein's point on the parallel between the Reformation and the present, and his hope that Klee's art might be a transitional work preceding a new spiritual turn. Klee's *Angelus Novus*, with its parody of the resurrected Christ and the interleaf of the image of Martin Luther, brings these two elements together. Surely their conjoining would not have been lost on Hausenstein, and this may have determined its inclusion and placement in the layout for *Kairuan*.

Klee's early catalogue number, 32 for the year, suggests the work was executed early in 1920, shortly after he had read the Grünewald book. We recall that Hausenstein's *Neue Rundschau* essay in which the critic characterized his art as "nihilism in every direction," as threatening "the end of painting," he had painted *The Dream* in "opposition" to Hausenstein. Might *Angelus Novus*, mounted over an image recalling the Reformation, also have been created in a similar spirit?

There is another probable connection to Grünewald's *Isenheim Altar* and to Hausenstein's account of it, one not previously noted in the literature. About the time Klee executed *Angelus Novus* he painted *Das Lamm* (*The Lamb*; FIG. 15),

which was also included in the Goltz retrospective (cat. no. 30). It bears Klee's oeuvre catalog number 39, only seven numbers after that of *Angelus Novus*. Its Christian symbolism is explicit, with a blood red cross emanating from behind the lamb's head; its eyes are pressed closed, shedding a large blood-red tear. The motif recalls the lamb in the crucifixion panel of the *Isenheim Altar* (FIG. 16). There, to the right of the crucified Christ, a lamb stands before the figure of John the Baptist. It was he who, in the Gospel of John (1:29), identifies Jesus with the words, "Behold the lamb of God, which taketh away the sins of the world." It holds a slender cross with its right front leg and blood flows from its breast into a chalice, a reference to the Eucharist as the blood of Christ. Of the lamb Hausenstein wrote: "the ultimate religious center of the *Isenheim Altar* is the infinitely conspicuous lamb, whose heart's blood leaps into the chalice."²⁰² That Klee's lamb bleeds from the eye and not from the heart is noteworthy: might this image also have been inspired by Hausenstein, namely by his lamentation on the ruptured bond between visual art and religion? There is more: Hausenstein writes that the lamb looks upward toward the crucified Christ²⁰³; Klee's lamb has no Christ to look at, nor does it gaze at the simple cross behind it; it turns its head sideways,

its weeping eyes tightly closed. Turning to the *Resurrection* Hausenstein describes the brilliant aureole around the risen Christ: "The world becomes a rainbow, heaven and earth become opal. The painter paints the *Resurrection of Christ*. [...] In the midst of a nervously starry sky of a black-green color stands or orbits a gigantic halo: outside green, then blue, violet, rose, orange, finally yellow."²⁰⁴ Is it coincidence that this palette, identified by Hausenstein with *The Resurrection*, is the very palette of *The Lamb*, applied in undulating bands of glowing color? Eyes shut, blind to its surroundings, the lamb mourns, yet around it the painting sings with vernal splendor. Might this be Klee again rebutting Hausenstein, affirming the glories of which contemporary painting is capable?²⁰⁵

Klee, it should be obvious, did not share Hausenstein's views about the desirability of reviving an art based on "the visibility of the world," which he called for in his book on the *Isenheim Altar*.²⁰⁶ "Art does not reproduce the visible but makes visible," Klee declared. This statement, which opens a text he completed in November 1918, should tell us what he must have thought of Hausenstein's hopes for the future of art, a text written, it should be noted, shortly after he had read the critic's essay on expressionism in *Die neue Rundschau*. Klee's text was subsequently published in an anthology entitled *Schöpferische Konfession*, creative credo.²⁰⁷ Hausenstein quotes from it extensively at the beginning of his final chapter but skips over this passage and the next two sentences to the fourth, in which Klee writes of how the purer the graphic means, the less they are suited to the "realistic representation of visible things."²⁰⁸

Two years after the publication of *Kairuan* Hausenstein brought out a third edition of

Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart, to which he appended a new chapter with the title: "Epilog aus dem Jahre 1922: Vom Sinn der Kunst" (Epilogue from the year 1922: On the meaning of art). Its eight pages offer a concise, final reckoning with "expressionism." "The endeavor is at an end. The strain is over. [...] The end came quickly."²⁰⁹ Yet, surprisingly, after his passionate dismissal of "expressionism" broadly defined, Hausenstein has positive words for a few artists: "I think of Picasso and Braque and Chagall and Kandinsky – yet I prefer to think of the "Eyes shut" painter-draughtsman Klee, whose non-representational (only seemingly non-representational) activity rose to the highest beauty of an irrationality of color and line, of poetry and music. Especially in Klee's sheets I see the ambiguous and paradoxical in the objectives of expressionistdom (*Expressionistentum*) and other related categories (for example those of Cubism) wonderfully elevated to the mysterious and profound productive elementary naturalness of consummate art – to that point where everything paradoxical is inexplicably reconciled with itself. Extremely few achieve that."²¹⁰

But as we read further in this text, it becomes clear that as before, Hausenstein regards the moment of this "expressionist" art as past. "What will now be? We will seek our art in the individuals who are more than expressionistic; in the chimerical visions of Kubin, Kokoschka, Beckmann."²¹¹ Their art may have indulged in fantasy, but at least it accepted the sovereignty of the objects of nature. But in declaring that henceforth one will seek out art in "individuals," Hausenstein has abandoned his dream of a collective style.

At the center of Hausenstein's epilogue is an extended discussion of the functions of art throughout history. Art "is not a purpose; it is a means; it is something absolutely secondary. [...] It is function – or it is

nothing at all.”²¹² Expressionism was an art with no function; its vacuity was an expression of the vacuity of the times.

Yet for Klee art did have a function. In his essay on graphic art he likened his art to a summer holiday, “a momentary change of view and of air,” transporting the viewer into a world that, as he put it, “strengthens us for the inevitable return to the grayness of the workday. Even more, may it help you to shed your shell and for a few moments imagine yourself as God. Always to look forward to evenings when the soul sits down to table to nourish its hungry nerves, to fill its flagging vessels with new juices.”²¹³ It was a function of art as private retreat and personal regeneration, far removed from Hausenstein’s dream of collective expression.

At bottom, the issue dividing Klee and Hausenstein was that of the relation between modern art and its public. Hausenstein, we recall, had declared Klee’s art the “most private of the private”; it threatened “to spell the end of the inalienable concept of an art public.” He never abandoned his belief that a socially meaningful art must have a broad public, no matter how rewarding its aesthetic qualities. In his late book, *Was bedeutet die moderne Kunst*, he restated this conviction unequivocally: it was all too clear that “modern art no longer fulfills any *social function*. Didactic endeavors to bring such an esoterically specialized thing ‘to the people’ are precisely a sign that it [...] is *no longer a social reality*. In actuality it is purely a matter for the aesthetically initiated [original emphasis].”²¹⁴ Yet even in that reactionary text he reaffirmed his unshakable admiration for Klee’s “irresistible, truly bewitching art,” with its “fathomless poesy” that “touched the transcendent,” even if it failed to engage and speak to a broad public.²¹⁵

From his youth Klee accepted the social marginality of modern art as a histor-

ical fact. “Uns tragt kein Volk,” the people do not support us, he famously acknowledged in his 1924 lecture at the Kunstverein Jena. Lacking that support, he lamented, he and his Bauhaus colleagues had failed to find *das Ganze*, the whole.²¹⁶ Yet he did not believe that art’s social marginality diminished its aesthetic value. He recognized that his art had a limited audience, but he had long come to terms with that. This comes through in a letter to Kubin, in which he reported on a visit of Rainer Maria Rilke to his Munich apartment “to look at watercolors; I was pleased by that. This man does not belong to our circle [...], and if my art yet speaks to him then I may already count him among my public, and a small public of fine heads is what I wish for.”²¹⁷

Exactly five years after its first Klee retrospective Neue Kunst Hans Goltz mounted a second, showing 214 works from the intervening period. Hausenstein reviewed this show, now writing in the *Frankfurter Zeitung*. To read this after *Kairuan* can be a startling experience: Hausenstein’s long, rapturous commentary is devoid of the mournful jeremiads that pervade his monograph: there’s no expression of longing for a return to the object, nature, and God; no anticipation of a Kokoschian future. Klee is no longer seen as a transitional figure but “a center of the times,” albeit paradoxically an “eccentric” one.²¹⁸ If in *Kairuan* he held that distinction because he was a *Ruinenmaler* “faithful to the unheard of confusion of the age,” in which persons and things had ceased to exist, he was now “the most delightful artist of his time, the most essential, the most comprehensive.” Hausenstein celebrates the “fantastic presence of *eroticism* in all, all of these sheets [...]. Were this language intelligible to everyone and I the inquisitor, I would ban these documents

of lust [original emphasis].”²¹⁹ And for those who relish “the painterly,” which according to *Kairuan* was unattainable in the fractured world of modernity, “here they have to an absolute degree what they love.” To be sure, Hausenstein openly acknowledges the sentiments expressed in his earlier commentaries, that this art was accessible only to a minority, and to “a very small one. [...] I don’t share this opinion if I ever shared it; today less than ever.”²²⁰

Concluding his review Hausenstein hails Klee as “a great artist,” in whom “one will one day measure the essential energies of a time that went far beyond the *ultima ratio* and formed its greatest beauty in the abyss or exuberance of the riddle.”²²¹ Here Hausenstein seems finally to have made his peace with modernity.

And yet: despite his effusive admiration for Klee Hausenstein never overcame his dark assessment of the state of modern art, a state determined by the general culture of modernity – it was no fault of the artists; they had been dealt a bad hand by the forces of history. Klee, creating an aesthetic utopia in this dystopian culture, made the most of this unhappy moment. This view emerges in Hausenstein’s *Kunstgeschichte*, 500-page historical survey of art from the ancient Near East to the present, published in 1928: “How can one characterize the situation since 1900? It lay between complete dissolution and the attempt at building anew. *Natural things*, that is those that can be experienced in the world of the directly visible, that had long been the subject matter of visual art were no longer painted and given form. In pictures, drawings, even in sculptures these things seemed ‘sabotaged’: they seemed shattered. The sabotage seemed profoundly melancholy. The pictures seemed to mourn disconsolately over these destroyed things. This much was clear: the old ‘things,’ the naturally grown, the sen-

suous things, were no longer present in pictures. The clay pipe of *Chardin*, the apple of *Courbet*, yes, even the asparagus or peach of *Manet* were no longer painted. One saw something else: shards – often undefinable broken pieces; fragments from an explosive collapse; splinters from the end of a world. Such things we saw most remarkably realized, even more remarkable than in *Picasso*’s art or that of his compatriot *Juan Gris*, in the watercolors of *Paul Klee* [original emphasis].”²²² Klee was still the *Ruinenmaler* after all.

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- ¹ In all the volumes of the Klee catalogue raisonné the number of exhibited objects is erroneously given as 371. The correct count should be 387, as verified to me by Osamu Okuda of the Zentrum Paul Klee in an e-mail of October 13, 2021. The Goltz catalog is accessible online at <http://sdr.lib.uiowa.edu/dada/Ararat/Klee/index.htm> [accessed September 21, 2021]. Beginning in 1911 Klee kept a running catalog of his production, assigning a sequential number (*Werknummer*) to each work within a given year. The highest *Werknummer* in the Goltz exhibition was 1920, 44, which is no. 2389 in the chronological catalogue raisonné comprising all media. See Helfenstein/Rümelin 1998–2004, vol. 3, p. 167.
- ² Hausenstein 1920b, p. 2. “Die Kunst Klees gehört vor allem ihr selbst: ihrer eigenen Intimität. Sie gehört weiter denen, die ihr wahlverwandt sind. Ausstellen kann hier nur heißen: Aufmerksamsten Gelegenheit geben – und etwa abwarten, ob noch von ferner her einer oder der andere hinzukomme. [...] Man bleibe also von Anfang an des Einen gewiss: dass Ausstellen im Fall dieses Künstlers einen Notbehelf bedeutet. Diese Kunst ist nicht öffentlichen Wesens. Sie ist das Privateste vom Privaten.” Klee wrote to Hausenstein, thanking him for “Ihre sehr fesselnde Arbeit im Feuilleton der M. N. N.” Letter from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein, June 6, 1920, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller – Nationalmuseum, Marbach. On Klee’s art as an art of privacy, see also Bourneuf 2013, pp. 37–42.
- ³ Hausenstein 1920b, p. 2. “Wenn es mir erlaubt wird, ein persönliches Wort zu sagen, so wäre es dies: daß mein Gefühl mit allen Fibern Ja sagt.”
- ⁴ Hausenstein 1913a, p. 22. “Das formal entscheidende ist immer die Frage, ob der Künstler einer Gemeinschaft dient oder ob er nur der Vermittler individueller Genüsse, der maître de plaisir sublimer Privatbegeisterung des einzelnen ist – ob er kollektiven Schönheitsbegriffen untergeordnet bleibt oder sich den ästhetischen Subjektivismen eines

allem Gemeinschaftsleben abholden

Kunstanachoretin opfert.”

- ⁵ Hausenstein 1911a, p. 325.
- ⁶ Hausenstein 1913b, p. 21. The exhibition included 157 paintings as well as thirty-one sculptures and was international in scope, with works by Georges Braque, Robert Delaunay, Juan Gris, Henri Matisse, and Pablo Picasso among others.
- ⁷ Hausenstein 1921.
- ⁸ Ibid, pp. 102, 104. “Wir [...] sind in die Epoche des Anarchischen und der Disgregation eingetreten. Das Subjektive ist wahrlich nicht das Höchste. Aber es ist in diesem scheelen Augenblick das Einzige; und ein Wunder des Himmels der Künstler, der dazu die Schönheit des Reims vermag. [...] Es ist undenkbar, daß Kunst, hat sie die Bedeutung und Schönheit der Konsequenz, in ihr anders aussehe als die Zeichnung Klees, deren Grenzen in der Spannweite des Exzesses seiner Subjektivität liegen. [...] Der Malerzeichner Klee nahm von der Zeit, was sie war. Er sah, was sie nicht war; sah ihr Vakuum, ihre Sprünge; sah ihre Ruinen und saß über ihnen. Sein Name bedeutet kein System. Seine Kunst ist irrational, selbst in der raffiniertesten Überlegung naiv, ist der unerhörten Verwirrung des Zeitalters hingegeben.” Hausenstein uses the German word “Disgregation”, and not “Desintegration.” The Oxford English Dictionary defines it as “separation of individuals from a company, or of component parts from a whole mass.” In chapter three (p. 17) he contrasts it with “Kongregation” rather than with “Integration.” For this reason “disgregation” is a more appropriate translation.
- ⁹ Hausenstein 1921, p. 95: “[...] vollends ist es sein Beruf, in einem sachlichen Stil Ruinenmaler zu sein; auch bis zum Naturalismus schonungslos. Mehr. Ihm bleibt es offen, ja ihm wird der Zwang auferlegt, den Spuk der Ruinen darzustellen. Gespenster und Gespensterchen malt er, zeichnet er nun; Geistergeschichten, die zwischen den brechenden Ver fugungen der früher Ding gewesenen Welt phosphoreszierend anheben; Irrlichter; Schatten, die von Gnomen erfüllt sind.”

¹⁰ On the roots of this campaign in the Wilhelmine era, see Lewis 2003.

¹¹ Gay 1968, p. 70.

¹² Letter to Hans and Ida Klee, February 2, 1902, in: Klee Briefe, vol. 1, p. 205. "Ein Paradies fand ich in der antiken Kunst. [...] Unsere Kunst spielt kulturell eine sehr belanglose Rolle. [...] Aber es macht nichts, man kam so zur Welt, und man findet sich drein."

¹³ Werner 2005, p. 6.

¹⁴ As cited in *ibid.*

¹⁵ He concedes as much in his late book, *Was bedeutet die moderne Kunst: Ein Wort der Besinnung*, (Hausenstein 1949, p. 11), but at the cost of rejecting most of modern art.

¹⁶ This is the topic of a book in progress. The present text was originally intended to be a chapter in that publication, but in the course of writing it became clear that its actual subject was the art criticism of Hausenstein rather than the art of Klee. I therefore decided to publish it as a separate piece.

¹⁷ Dresdner 2015.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 2, 4.

¹⁹ See Benjamin W., 2003, p. 392.

²⁰ In recent decades Hausenstein, and particularly *Kairuan*, has finally and deservedly begun to receive the attention of scholars in the world of Klee scholarship. The book was ignored in the literature until 1982, when O. K. Werckmeister published a long, thoroughly detailed article in German for the catalog of an exhibition on Klee's Tunisian journey (Werckmeister 1982), an account that has until now remained unmatched in its close reading of *Kairuan* and the circumstances of its writing. It was Werckmeister's article, which I first read in 1984, that stimulated my own interest in this topic. He subsequently incorporated much of the material from this pioneering article in his book-length English-language monograph, integrating it into a richly documented narrative on Klee's career during the years 1914–1920 (Werckmeister 1989). While Christine Hopfengart offered a cursory discussion of *Kairuan* in her survey of Klee's critical reception (Hopfengart 1989, pp. 44–46), Claudia Öhlschläger was the first scholar after

Werckmeister to write at length on *Kairuan*, including a discussion of the central issue of Hausenstein's orientalizing of Klee (Öhlschläger 2000). Five years later she productively revisited Hausenstein's monograph in an essay on Rilke, Klee, and the problem of abstraction, in which Hausenstein plays a central role. A decade later Annie Bourneuf drew extensively on *Kairuan* in a major study of the interplay between word and image in Klee's works of the late 1910s and early 1920s (Bourneuf 2015a). Manfred Clemenz became the first since Werckmeister to offer an analysis of *Kairuan* in the context of Klee's critical reception (Clemenz 2016, pp. 163–172). He writes that "mit Hausensteins Biographie nicht nur eine eindringliche Schilderung des Menschen Klee vorliegt, sondern zugleich eine kunsttheoretische Diskussion deutlich wird, die von erheblicher Bedeutung für die künstlerische Entwicklung des Malers war" (p. 163). With the publication of Kerstin Bitar's dissertation (Bitar 2018), Hausenstein's vast written corpus finally received the attention it merited. Her work and her generous responses to my queries have been an indispensable resource for my own efforts in this essay. In 2014, Michael Haerdter and Kenneth Croose Parry, Hausenstein's son-in-law, brought out a new German edition of *Kairuan*, with a shortened title, *Kairuan: Eine Geschichte vom Maler Klee* (Hausenstein 2014), for which they unfortunately revised Hausenstein's selection and placement of illustrations. This was carried over in the subsequent English translation, in which the original title, of crucial significance for Hausenstein's concept, was now changed to *Kairuan: Or How Paul Klee Became a Painter*. Throughout this essay all page references are to the original German edition and all translations are my own.

²¹ Werner 2005, pp. 33–34.

²² The subject of his dissertation was the reunification of Regensburg with Bavaria in 1810. See *ibid.*, p. 10.

²³ Bitar 2018, pp. 45–48.

- ²⁴ Hausenstein 1911b, pp. 116–117. “Meier-Graefe ist aber der Schriftsteller, der eindringlich wie kein zweiter in die Genealogie der modernen Malerei hineingesehen hat. [...] Dieser Schriftsteller, dem Deutschland und die kunstgeschichtliche Weltliteratur Ungeheures danken, ist den anderen – die von ihm lernen könnten – so zuwider, dass sie die Dinge umgehen, die auch in ihren Augen für ihn sprechen müssten.” The most extensive study of Hausenstein is Bitar 2018. See also Migge 1967, which includes a detailed chronology of Hausenstein’s life (pp. 9–25), and Werner 2005.
- ²⁵ Meier-Graefe 1904 vol. 1, p. 25. Modified translation from Meier-Graefe 1908, vol. 1, p. 13.
- ²⁶ Ibid., vol. 1, p. 38. Modified translation from Meier-Graefe 1908, vol. 1, p. 20.
- ²⁷ Ibid., vol. 1, p. 10. The issue of art’s status with the larger public was a major concern in the German Reich. On this see the excellent study by Beth Irwin Lewis, Lewis 2003.
- ²⁸ Bitar 2018, pp. 43–44.
- ²⁹ In 1910 Hausenstein published four articles in *Sozialistische Monatshefte* on educational policy and school reform.
- ³⁰ On these activities see Werner 2005, pp. 47–49, 58–59, and Bitar 2018, pp. 51–52.
- ³¹ See Hausenstein 1909a, 1909b, 1912a, 1913a and 1914a.
- ³² Hausenstein 1913a, pp. 6, 10.
- ³³ Ibid., p. 2.
- ³⁴ Ibid., p. 18. “Die Idee des Stils bedeutet, wenn sie ganz streng gefaßt wird, die festgeschlossene Synthese aller Formen der Existenz. [...] Der Stil ist [...] das feindlichste aller Widerspiele des Individuationsprinzips.”
- ³⁵ Hausenstein 1913a, p. 1. “Die Kunst unserer Tage ist die Katastrophe des Naturalismus und der Sieg des Stils.”
- ³⁶ Hausenstein 1913c, pp. 758–794.
- ³⁷ Hausenstein 1913c, p. 775. “Da die Zeit nun ohne positiven Ausdruck war, wurde die Kunst historisch. Es entstand die ästhetische Parabel. Es entstand die Malerei des ‘als ob’. Ingres vollendete die Linie, die David begonnen hatte, und machte aus ihr ein Dokument persönlichster Kultur. Delacroix malte, als ob die Bourgeoisie des Louis-Philippe das Publikum des Tizian oder des Veronese wäre. [...] Denn aus dem Leben der Gesellschaft führte kein unmittelbarer Weg zur Kunst und die Kunst vollzog sich so sehr als Spezialität des Ateliers, daß man ihre einzige positive Beziehung zur Zeit in ihrer Teilnahme am Prozeß der Individuierung und am Prozeß der Arbeitsteilung finden mag. [...] Die Malerei wurde zur Privatsache [...]”
- ³⁸ Meier-Graefe 1904, vol 1, p. 16.
- ³⁹ Ibid., vol. 1, p. 17.
- ⁴⁰ Hausenstein 1912b, p. 622.
- ⁴¹ Hausenstein 1914a, p. 14.
- ⁴² Hausenstein soon became reconciled to the phenomenon of the commercial art gallery as a public institution. In 1916, he wrote a long introduction to the stock catalog of Munich’s Thannhauser gallery. See Hausenstein 1916a, pp. 7–28.
- ⁴³ Hausenstein 1914a, p. 278.
- ⁴⁴ For a detailed account see Haxthausen 1990. Some of the material in the present essay is adapted from that article.
- ⁴⁵ Hausenstein 1914a, p. 13.
- ⁴⁶ Hausenstein 1913c, p. 770.
- ⁴⁷ Hausenstein 1914a, p. 13.
- ⁴⁸ Hausenstein 1913b, pp. 8–9. Here and throughout I am preserving gendered pronouns where they appear in the original historical text.
- ⁴⁹ Klee 1912, p. 701. “Die Modernität ist eine Erleichterung der Individualität, auf neuem Gebiet verändern sich auch Wiederholungen zu neuen Ichformen. Hier kann man nicht von Schwachheit reden, wenn sich viele an einem Platz vereinigen, denn jeden treibt es, da eher ein ausgesprochenes Ich zu werden.” Reprinted in: Klee, Schriften, p. 109. Shortly before reviewing the Moderner Bund exhibition Klee wrote to Alfred Kubin, reflecting on his recent trip to Paris: “Von Paris habe ich allerdings allerlei starke Eindrücke mitgebracht. So sehr ich die neuesten Bestrebungen auch gerade da schätzen lernte, sehe ich doch ein, daß ich weniger forschen, und noch mehr als bisher an die Ausarbeitung des Persönlichen gehen soll.” Letter of May 19, 1912, in: Klee, Briefe an Kubin, p. 83.

- ⁵⁰ In a diary entry from Naples, dated March 1902 but redacted by Klee during the war, he described his impressions of the poverty he witnessed in Naples: "Unten am Hafen sucht man durch eine unheimliche Welt zu dringen, die ganz anders klingt als im Santa Lucia Lied. Sind das Menschen, da unten? Hässlich elend, krank liegt in der Sonne herum, lausig zerlumpt, halbnackt. Neutral treibts mich zu ihnen ohne Barmherzigkeit, mit wissensdurstiger Abscheu. Eine Wollust des Künstlermenschen, sich so voll infizieren zu lassen. Ich lächle in der Empörung. Ich weiss meine Kunst braucht das als Grundlage." Klee, *Tagebücher*, no. 389, pp. 122–123. On his diaries see Kersten's afterword in *ibid.*, pp. 589–591. For more on Klee's social attitudes and his brief fascination with socialism, see Haxthausen 1981, pp. 103–112. For a fundamental article on the dating for Klee's later redaction of his diaries, see Geelhaar 1979b, pp. 246–260. On the dating of the "Italian diary" see *ibid.*, p. 251.
- ⁵¹ Klee to Lily Stumpf, January 31, 1905, in: Klee, *Briefe*, vol. 1, p. 476. "Gelesen habe ich [...] etwas Interessantes; von Oscar Wilde einen Essay: 'Der Socialismus und die Seele des Menschen,' der Inhalt ist der Nachweis, daß Socialismus und Individualismus zu vereinen sind, daß also der Künstler Socialist sein könne."
- ⁵² Klee, letter to Lily Stumpf, February 19, 1905, in: *ibid.*, vol. 1, p. 482. "Man muß das Menschentum nur in seinen kulturellen Spitzen aufsuchen, um zur Hochachtung zu gelangen. Wenn der Socialismus jeder Veranlagung das geeignete Milieu verschaffen will und kann, so bin auch ich Socialist. Doch fehlt mir da der Glaube, wie in den meisten Dingen. Aber dagegen würde ich nie sein, weil er die einzige anständige Bewegung ist." Two years earlier he had expressed contempt for accusations of fraud when, in the Reichstag elections of June 1903, the Social Democratic Party posted gains of 40%, securing roughly one quarter of the seats in parliament. "Wie plump man sich in Deutschland über den Fortschritt ärgert!"
- Letter to Lily Stumpf, July 1, 1903, in: *ibid.*, vol. 1, p. 333.
- ⁵³ Letter to Lily Stumpf, June 28, 1905, in *ibid.*, vol. 1, p. 511. "Meine Hoffnungslosigkeit, daß der Menschheit je zu helfen sei, kann nicht größer werden. / [...] Ich will nur noch aufklären; zu retten ist nichts. Auch der Sozialismus ist nur ein Almosen. So wie die Wohltätigkeit unserer Zeit innerhalb der kapitalistischen Einrichtungen nicht mehr ist als ein Almosen, so könnten sozialistische Einrichtungen innerhalb der 'göttlichen Weltordnung' der Menschheit nicht mehr sein."
- ⁵⁴ See his letter to Kubin, from May 12, 1919 (Klee, *Briefe an Kubin*, p. 93), in which he expressed his sympathy for the recently violently suppressed communist *Räterepublik*. "So wenig dauerhaft diese kommunistische Republik [sic!] von Anfang an schien, so gab sie doch Gelegenheit zur Überprüfung der subjektiven Existenz-Möglichkeiten in einem solchen Gemeinwesen. Ohne positives Ergebnis war sie nicht. Natürlich eine zugespitzte, individualistische Kunst ist zum Genuß durch die Gesamtheit nicht geeignet, sie ist kapitalistischer Luxus. Aber wir sind doch wohl mehr als Kuriositäten für reiche Snobs. Und das was an uns irgendwie darüber hinaus Ewigkeitswerten zustrebt, das würde im kommunistischen Gemeinwesen eher Förderung erfahren können. Die befruchtende Wirkung unseres Beispiels würde sich durch anders geartete Kanalisierung auf breiterer Basis abspielen. Wir würden als ideelle Versuchsstation nicht neue Erfinder abrichten, die dann doch keine wären, sondern nur Erfinder-Masken (wie die Akademiker ihren Lehrern gleichen wie Kinder einem Vater) sondern wir würden die Ergebnisse unserer Erfindertätigkeit dem Volkskörper zuleiten können. Diese neue Kunst könnte dann ins Handwerk eindringen und eine große Blüte hervorbringen. Denn Akademien gäbe es nicht mehr, sondern nur Kunstschulen für Handwerker. [...] Lieber Kubin, vielleicht interessiert Sie das nicht so sehr, aber es hat mich zeitweise sehr beschäftigt. Daß ich deswegen von nichts Wesentlichem abwich,

würde Ihnen meine Secessionskollektion erweisen." For commentary on this letter, see Haxthausen 1979, pp. 129–130, note 10; Werckmeister 1989, pp. 175–180; and Bourneuf 2022, pp. 42–44.

- ⁵⁵ Klee to his mother, Ida Klee, April 4, 1913, in: Klee, Briefe, vol. 2, p. 777. In a letter to Franz Marc, dated January 23, 1912, Kandinsky reported sending the critic "a couple of drawings by Klee." Kandinsky/Marc 1983, p. 123. The connection may also have occurred through Alfred Kubin, who had been friendly with Klee since 1910 and with Hausenstein since 1911. In her monograph on Hausenstein, Kerstin Bitar writes that this encounter at the Klees' Schwabing apartment was their first. Bitar 2018, p. 231.
- ⁵⁶ Through the intercession of Franz Blei, an editor at Hyperion, Klee had earlier met with Meier-Graefe in January 1909 to show him his ink drawings. Meier-Graefe's reaction: "Vielleicht wird's was!" See Klee, Tagebücher, no. 853, p. 288; also *ibid.*, Anhang p. 499.
- ⁵⁷ Hausenstein 1913b, p. 16.
- ⁵⁸ Hausenstein 1914a, pp. 307–308. A note at the beginning of the book states that the manuscript was completed at the end of 1913.
- ⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, 307. "Auch auf dem Gebiet der Graphik hat die moderne Bewegung Talente durchgesetzt, die innerhalb einer allgemeinen Modernität bis zum Exzentrischen persönlich sind."
- ⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, 307–08. "Seine Zeichnungen [...] sind der letzte überhaupt noch graphisch materialisierbare psychologische Reflex sinnlicher und mehr noch übersinnlicher Erlebnisse. [...] Die Vision zittert in der Luft wie ein halber Gedanke, der sich nicht bestimmen läßt. Aus diesem absolut Vagen macht Klee etwas formal ungewöhnlich Bestimmtes. Man hat ähnliche Gefühle wie bei Picasso; man hat das Gefühl einer bis zur Kindlichkeit sublimen Verderbtheit, die aber keinen Moment im Stofflichen bleibt, sondern sich sofort mit größter Intensität in künstlerische Anschauung umsetzt und das verwischteste Erlebnis mit einer Handschrift von namenloser, dennoch präziser Erotik niederzuschreiben weiß. Begriffe wie Dekadenz sind hier sinnlos: die

Intensität und die Schärfe der Form überwindet zuletzt jegliche Zerrüttung, und am Ende bleibt nichts übrig als der sichere Eindruck einer in ihrer Weise vollendeten Musik." Picasso received one of the mere thirty-two illustrations in the book, namely the cubist *Man with Clarinet*, 1912. Klee received none.

- ⁶¹ Klee to Kubin, undated (December 1914), in: Klee, Briefe an Kubin, p. 86. "Hausensteins Buch habe ich heut erhalten. Wir kommen gut weg, wir zwei. Und es ist trotzdem ein ganz normales Buch [...] und seine kühle Vernunft wird Gutes für uns wirken." Hausenstein devoted two laudatory pages to Kubin. See Hausenstein 1914a, pp. 281–282.
- ⁶² Neue Münchner Secession 1914, pp. 16–17, nos. 71–78. Numbers 74 and 78 were watercolors of Kairuan, incorrectly listed in the catalogue as "Kaizuan."
- ⁶³ Hausenstein 1914b, p. 334. "Klee lebt in einer Isolierung, die ihn dem Örtlichen ganz entrückt. Seine köstlichen Aquarelle aus Afrika sind die Musik eines Überhobenen, der in einer wundervollen Verwirrung die Beziehungen zu allem Natürlich-Positiven und vollends zu festen lokalen Möglichkeiten verlor und sich nun restlos in der einsamen Geistigkeit seines Lebens konzentriert." This is an example of Hausenstein's disposition to fantastical projection. Klee's twelve-day Tunisian sojourn was far from detached from the world, as his diary entries and correspondence attest. He had great fun with his travel companions and fellow artists August Macke and Louis Moilliet. On August 19, 1913 he wrote to Moilliet: "Nach Tunis allein zu fahren ist's nicht was ich eigentlich wollte! Es sollte eine richtige Studienfahrt werden, wo einer den andern anregt." Baumgartner 2014, p. 267. See also Hopfengart 2014, pp. 220–231, and Baumgartner 2014, pp. 108–27.
- ⁶⁴ Hausenstein 1913c, p. 790.
- ⁶⁵ Hausenstein 1913a, p. 7.
- ⁶⁶ Hausenstein 1914c, p. 872–874.
- ⁶⁷ Klee to Hausenstein, December 19, 1914, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller – Nationalmuseum, Marbach. "[...] dass der Verlag Kunst und Dekoration 'unverbindlichst'

eine Ansichtskollektion meiner neuesten Blätter haben möchte. Ob durch eine geeignete Auswahl die Chancen verbessert werden können oder sollen?? Jedenfalls wäre ich Ihnen für die Beihilfe an einer solchen Auswahl dankbar. Sie müssten die definitive Wahl ja dann Ihren speziellen Interessen doch anpassen. Unser Unternehmen ist u. bleibt kühn.”

⁶⁸ For most of 1916 and 1917, Hausenstein was stationed in Belgium as part of the German war colony. During this time he published little on modern art, but in 1916 he wrote, at the invitation of Franz Marc’s widow, Maria, the catalog preface for a memorial exhibition mounted by the Munich New Secession (Marc had fallen in Verdun in March of that year). Klee was originally commissioned to contribute a brief biographical essay, but Maria Marc, who was critical of his attitude toward the war, preferred Hausenstein, so Klee deferred to her and politely withdrew. In his text Hausenstein reaffirmed the values that characterized his pre-war writings. “Seine Kunst erquickte nicht nur das Auge und die schöne Empfindung. Sie zielte weiter und traf tiefer. [...] Sie war teilhaftig der Voraussetzungen, die den Menschen mit allem im tiefsten Sinne Öffentlichen verbinden. Sie war keine Privatangelegenheit [...]. So lebt in dieser Kunst ein dem politischen Geist von fern vergleichbarer Genius – ein Element umfassender gesellschaftlicher Gesinnung.” Hausenstein 1916c, pp. 7–8. In short, in these respects Marc’s art stood in the strongest contrast to how Hausenstein would come to define that of Klee. On this episode, see Werckmeister 1989, pp. 76–80.

⁶⁹ Sulzer 1982, p. 13; Migge 1967, p. 53.

⁷⁰ See Geelhaar 1979a, p. 30.

⁷¹ Klee to Lily Klee, November 15, 1917, in: Klee, Briefe, vol. 2, pp. 885–886. Hausenstein had joined the newspaper’s staff on November 1st. See his letter of November 4, 1917 to Katharina Kippenberg, in: Hausenstein 1999, p. 50.

⁷² Typically for him, Hausenstein did not identify specific works. Directness (*Unmittelbarkeit*), he complained, was the quality lacking in most of

the work in the exhibition, which he found derivative, “academic.” Expressionism had become like a “superstition.” Hausenstein 1918a, p. 2.

⁷³ Ibid. “Das Urteil ist vollkommen persönlich gemeint; es verpflichtet niemand. Zumal bleibt die Einschätzung Klees sich bewusst, daß sie eine irgendwie allgemeingültige Urteilsnorm weder geben kann noch will; seine Zeichnung ist so subjektiv und so voll von grundsätzlich Problematischem, daß sie objektiv-allgemeinen Kunstmaßstäben gegenüber unmöglich geltend gemacht werden kann.”

⁷⁴ Klee to Lily Klee, March 19, 1918, in: Klee, Briefe, vol. 2, p. 911.

⁷⁵ Hausenstein presented the lecture to the Bund Deutscher Gelehrter und Künstler and the Deutsche Gesellschaft 1914. It was subsequently published in *Die neue Rundschau*. See Hausenstein 1918b.

⁷⁶ Ibid., pp. 914–915.

⁷⁷ Ibid., p. 916. In an autobiography published in 1946 in a bilingual edition of selected Baudelaire poems in his translation, Hausenstein wrote that up to 1918 his writing was mostly “soziologisch orientiert”; after 1918 it was “in zunehmenden Maße auf die religiösen Aspekte der Kunstgeschichte gerichtet.” Quoted after Bitar 2018, pp. 80–81.

⁷⁸ Hausenstein 1918b, p. 927. “[D]er Pendel hat durchgeschwungen; das Positive der Zukunft liegt offenbar in einer neuen und frommen Bescheidung auf die Natur [...].”

⁷⁹ Ibid., p. 930. “[...] aufs neue von unten auf die Natur zu bewundern; die unsäglich verlästerte; und des Satzes zu gedenken, den der angeblich überwundene Cézanne gesagt hat: ‘[...] Es ist die Hauptsache, Poussin im Angesicht der Natur noch einmal zu malen; das ist alles.’” This was a drastic shift! In *Bildende Kunst der Gegenwart* he had written: “Der Wandel der Kunstanschauung läßt sich zuletzt auf nichts andres zurückführen als auf eine Katastrophe des Begriffes Natur. Der Inhalt des Begriffs hat sich verändert. [...] [D]er Begriff der Natur [ist] heute schon ins Geistige, ja ins Übernatürliche gekehrt.” Hausenstein 1914a, p. 21.

⁸⁰ Ibid., p. 921. "Im Expressionismus [...] wurde der Versuch gemacht, der Darstellung der Gegenstandsform die Darbietung des absoluten Mittels gegenüberzustellen. Das ist der Sinn der Entwicklung von Matisse bis Kandinsky, von Picasso bis Klee. Bis zu einem gewissen Grad ist die Malerei und Doktrin Kandinskys einfach der Versuch, dem Ding an sich nicht einmal die Form an sich, sondern das emanzipierte Mittel, das Mittel an sich entgegenzustellen: die absolute Farbe auf dem Niveau der Selbstversorgung. Das nämliche vollzieht sich auf dem Boden einer sublimierten Begabung bei dem Graphiker und Maler Klee. Seine Zeichnungen sind, von einem entfernten Motiv aus bewegt, der Versuch: den Reiz, den Tiefsinn, die Leichtfertigkeit, den Witz, das Pathos, das Schreckliche des bloßen graphischen Strichs zu abstrahieren und das graphische Mittel in allen erdenklichen Kombinationen auf der Höhe solcher Abstraktion festzuhalten – also alle mögliche Formalität des Graphischen zu destillieren. Es ist die schier unvergleichliche Bedeutung dieses Künstlers, daß keiner dies je so persönlich-zwanghaft und ausschließlich tat wie er – Picasso etwa ausgenommen, der aber (als Romane mit klassizistischen Neigungen) kaum die musikalisch abgründige Tiefe Klees besitzt."

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Ibid., p. 927. "Alles, was der Expressionismus hervorgebracht hat, ist – soweit es sittlich und künstlerisch taugt – bewußt oder unbewußt Brücke zum Metaphysischen. Man dachte, dem Metaphysischen um so näher zu sein, je mehr man abstrahierte. Die aufwühlende und wieder wie Rokoko entzückende, wie Biedermeiertum sensitiv-harmlose, ironisierbare und verfälschte Kunst Klees gäbe freilich ein fast überzeugendes Beispiel der Möglichkeit solchen Wollens. Aber ihre Subjektivität ist so schwer erreichbar, daß sie zugleich das Ende der Malerei bedeutet: dem Nihilismus nach allen Seiten. / Es ist möglich, daß die Reise der Kunst dahin geht. Das ist nicht abzusehen. Davon sei also auch nicht die Rede."

⁸³ Hausenstein 1918a, p. 2. "Vielleicht ergibt sich einmal Gelegenheit, die äußerst pointierte Art Klees, zu der man fast nur ein persönlich zugespitztes Verhältnis haben kann, in besonderer Studie einem weiteren Kreis (wiewohl niemals einem großen) versuchsweise zu vermitteln."

⁸⁴ Postcard from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein, May 22, 1918, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller Nationalmuseum, Marbach. See also Klee's letter to his mother and his sister, Mathilde Klee, from July 8 of that year: "Das Buch von Hausenstein ist vorläufig nur Plan, aber er wird es sicher durchsetzen mit seiner großen Energie." Klee, Briefe, vol. 2, p. 926.

⁸⁵ Postcard to Lily Klee, August 19, 1918, in: *ibid.*, vol. 2, p. 933. "Der Hausensteinsche Aufsatz, so schmeichelhaft er für mich ist, hat doch wieder eine Art Opposition in mir hervorgerufen, und ich malte ein streng organisiertes Stück *Der Traum*, eines meiner schlagendsten Blätter, auf grobes Papierleinen mit Gipsgrund." Werckmeister, evidently overlooking the publication of Hausenstein's March lecture in the July issue of *Die neue Rundschau*, assumed that Klee was reacting to Hausenstein's review of the New Secession exhibition in the March 18 issue of *Münchener Neueste Nachrichten*. See Werckmeister 1982, p. 79. He did not correct the error in his later monograph. In his view, "[t]he disagreement with Hausenstein surely referred to the latter's opinion that Klee lacked the sense of firm composition which Hausenstein deemed to be the most essential feature of modern art with claims to public relevance." Werckmeister 1989, pp. 129–130.

⁸⁶ It is far from obvious in what sense Klee considered *Der Traum* to be an expression of "opposition" to Hausenstein. In his *Neue Rundschau* article the critic hadn't criticized Klee on the basis of his formal qualities, but for his ostensibly unfathomable "subjectivity," his "nihilism," which he perceived as a threat to the very survival of painting. The explanation may lie elsewhere. In a diary entry, dated the same day as his postcard to Lily (and in this case we

are dealing with the original diary, not a later redaction – the diary from March 1916 through December 1918 was not redacted by Klee), Klee characterized his watercolor not as “ein streng organisiertes Stück” but as “ein streng organisches Stück,” a rigorously organic piece. Entry for August 19, 1918, in: Klee, Tagebücher, no. 1126a, p. 464. There is no mention of the organic in Hausenstein’s *Neue Rundschau* essay but the term was fundamental in a book he was beginning at the time, *Vom Geist des Barock* (On the spirit of the Baroque). He completed the manuscript in the summer of 1919 and the book, with an imprint of 1920, must have appeared by the end of 1919. The first chapter is titled “Das Organische,” and the word recurs throughout the book as a defining feature of the Baroque.

⁸⁷ Hausenstein 1919b, p. 51. “[...] ihre Subjektivität ist so schwer erreichbar, daß sie zugleich das Ende des unveräußerlichen Begriffs der künstlerischen Öffentlichkeit zu werden droht. Es ist möglich, daß die Reise der Kunst dahin geht. Das ist nicht abzusehen. Dazu: es ist nicht zu wünschen.”

⁸⁸ For a detailed account of the episode, see Werckmeister 1989, pp. 189–192, 213–220.

⁸⁹ Letter of July 2, 1919, cited in *ibid.*, p. 190.

⁹⁰ The anonymous author wrote: “Es ist nicht meines Amtes, und es liegt mir vollkommen fern, über Klees künstlerische Bedeutung im allgemeinen ein Urteil abzugeben. Aber Klee als Lehrer und Führer unserer künstlerischen Jugend erscheint nicht nur mir als ein unmöglicher Gedanke. Es heißt, alles auf den Kopf stellen, will man die jungen Leute mit dem letzten Raffinement beginnen lassen. Die “Sturm”-Kunstschule, deren Wirkung wir schauernd erlebten, sollte vor solchen Versuchen zurückschrecken [...]” Anonymous 1919, pp. 145–146.

⁹¹ As cited in Werckmeister 1989, p. 217. “In den M. N. N. ist die Kunst Klees wiederholt mit Worten tiefer Sympathie gedacht worden. Um so mehr besteht selbstverständlich die Verpflichtung, zu betonen, daß der Gedanke einer derartigen Berufung Klees durch und durch verfehlt wäre. Er wäre deshalb verfehlt,

weil er am eigentlichen Wert Klees, an der absoluten Subjektivität und Irrationalität seines Arbeitens (die nicht nur allem Lehrhaften entgegengesetzt, sondern beinahe aller Ausdeutung entzogen ist), geraden Wegs vorbeigeht. Man lasse Klee in der Sphäre, in der er einzig denkbar ist: in der Abseitigkeit seiner bedingungslos und ungehemmt persönlichen Phantasie und in der verborgenen Zauberwelt seiner Geige.”

⁹² *Ibid.*, p. 218.

⁹³ *Ibid.*

⁹⁴ Hausenstein knew Hölzel well and cited him several times in Hausenstein 1913b, pp. 12, 15–16.

⁹⁵ Hausenstein informed Klee of the signing of the contract in a letter dated November 1919.

⁹⁶ Letter from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein, December 9, 1919, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller – Nationalmuseum, Marbach.

⁹⁷ Hausenstein 1919/1920, pp. 115–127. Although this special, unnumbered issue is dated 1919/1920, indicating that it appeared at the turn of the year, it seems that it must have appeared several months into the new year. In the June issue of *Das Kunstblatt*, Paul Westheim, the magazine’s editor, reviewed Hausenstein’s article, writing as if the issue had recently appeared. See Westheim 1920. In April Leopold Zahn reviewed a lecture, which he sarcastically dubbed a “Leichenrede,” a funeral oration, by Hausenstein, a lecture that, based on Zahn’s description, seems consistent with the contents of the article. See Zahn 1920a, p. 53. Less than two months later Hausenstein learned in a letter from Klee that he had given his consent to Zahn to prepare a monograph on him (Zahn 1920b). Responding to this “peinliche Überraschung,” Hausenstein wrote Klee that in effect “kommt Ihre Zustimmung natürlich einer Unterstützung dieser Sabotage gleich [...] gegen mich und mein Buch [...] Dass ein zweites Buch über Klee nicht nur sachlich überflüssig, sondern für Sie sogar vielleicht schädlich und mir jedenfalls nicht gleichgültig sein konnte, war doch unter allen Umständen klar. Es ist mir schmerzlich, dass Sie daran nicht gedacht haben – wenn mir auch fern liegt

Ihnen einen Vorwurf zu machen.” Copy of the letter from Wilhelm Hausenstein to Paul Klee, June 1, 1920, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern.

⁹⁸ Hausenstein 1919/1920, pp. 120, 123.

⁹⁹ Ibid., pp. 119–120.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid., p. 123.

¹⁰¹ In a series of lectures for a general audience at the Kunsthalle Mannheim, Hausenstein argued that the very essence of artistic activity was the observation of *things*: “Der Künstler hat gar kein anderes Ziel als die Anschauung der Dinge. Er sieht an. Er betrachtet. Er hat dabei keinerlei Gedanken.” Hausenstein 1914d, p. 9. Might Hausenstein have got the idea of the disappearance of things from Rainer Maria Rilke? In the poet’s second Rodin essay, first delivered as a lecture in 1907, he wrote that he saw “die Tragik dieses Werkes auf dem Grunde seiner Größe. Ich fühle deutlicher als je, daß in diesen Dingen die Skulptur unaufhaltsam zu einer Macht angewachsen ist, wie niemals seit der Antike. Aber diese Plastik ist in eine Zeit geboren worden, die keine Dinge hat, keine Häuser, kein Äußeres. Denn das Innere, das diese Zeit ausmacht, ist ohne Form, unfaßbar: es fließt.” Rilke 1920, p. 114. For a discussion of Hausenstein, Klee, and Rilke concerning this issue, see Öhlschläger 2005. Rilke and Hausenstein became friends in 1915, and the poet was a witness in Hausenstein’s marriage to Margot Lipper in May 1919. Their only child, Renée Marie, was named after the poet.

¹⁰² Hausenstein 1914d, p. 125.

¹⁰³ Spengler 1920.

¹⁰⁴ Worringer 1921, p. 10. This was the publication of a lecture given on October 19, 1920 to the Munich branch of the Deutsche Goethegesellschaft.

¹⁰⁵ Hausenstein’s early writings contain many references to the dialectic operative within history. See, for example, Hausenstein 1913c, p. 768, in which he characterizes the Baroque as reaction, “nicht [...] in dem polemischen Sinn des politischen Werktagkampfes, sondern Reaktion im Sinn der Dialektik der Geschichte, die immer in Thesis und Antithesis weiter schreitet.”

¹⁰⁶ Spengler 1920, p. 150.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid., pp. 303–304.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid., p. 397. Spengler also took a swipe at the concept that underlay Hausenstein’s *Der nackte Mensch*, “daß der nackte menschliche Körper der vornehmste und eigentliche Gegenstand der bildenden Kunst sei. Man hat, wie es scheint, nie bemerkt, wie selten diese Gattung ist, ein Einzelfall, eine Ausnahme, nichts weniger als eine Regel.” Ibid., p. 310.

¹⁰⁹ Ibid., p. 398.

¹¹⁰ Letter from Wilhelm Hausenstein to Paul Klee, November 1919, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, inv. no. SFK Ko P Hau 7. As Bitar observes, “Von Anfang an ist offensichtlich, dass es sich nicht um eine gewöhnliche Biographie, sondern tatsächlich um eine Erzählung handelt, die einen sehr aufmerksamen Leser erfordert.” Bitar 2018, p. 236.

¹¹¹ Both drafts are preserved among Hausenstein’s papers in the Deutsches Literatur-Archiv in Marbach. I am grateful to the late Kenneth Croose Parry for providing me with copies.

¹¹² I attribute the manuscript of the draft as dictated to Margot Lipper, his second wife and a Belgian, because of numerous spelling and grammatical errors (was the dictation part of Hausenstein’s effort to teach her German?). The couple had met during Hausenstein’s assignment in Belgium. She moved to Munich in November 1918, the month in which he divorced his first wife, Marga. Margot and Hausenstein married on May 7, 1919. See Werner 2005, p. 70.

¹¹³ Hausenstein, Kairuan Draft B, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach, p. 10: “[...] seine Malerei im höchsten Grad beunruhigend, sein Wesen abgeschlossen, unauffindbar.”

¹¹⁴ Ibid., pp. 14–15, 18. “Die Dinge verfolgen mich. Meine Gedanken auf Spaziergänge [sic] nehmen ihre Farben und ihre Striche an. Ich kann nicht weiter denken aus meine [sic] eigenen Gedanken heraus. Klee kommt dazwischen, daß heißt seine Farben und seine Strichen [sic]. Höre ich Musik, so schieb [sic] sich ein Aquarell von ihm dazwischen. Graue Straßenwände werden halluziniert mit seinen

Aquarellen und mit seinen Strichen. Inschriften von Kindern werden gefährlich. [...] Es wird Manie bei mir, Hoffmannisch. Ich muß mich befreien. Ich erfinde das Märchen von der Entwicklungsgeschichte der Kunst / [...] Linie vom sichtbaren Ding zum Nichts; zum bloßen Mittel das mit sich selbst spielt. Aber ist es ein Nichts? Oh! Nein. Es ist nur eine bis im innersten reflektierte Welt. Da außen keine Gegenstände mehr sind und innen kein Glaube ist bleibt nichts übrig als die innerste [sic] Reflexe zu malen. Nerven. Vielleicht ist das alles einen Naturalismus nach innen zu statt nach aussen zu." It's noteworthy that the draft here adopts the spelling of Meier-Graefe's classic survey, *Entwicklungsgeschichte*. See Meier-Graefe 1904.

¹¹⁵ The term "Expressionism," previously so central to Hausenstein's writing on the art of his time, occurs only once in *Kairuan*: "Expressionismus und Klee: Quadrat und Kreis" (p. 104), thus isolating him as an anomaly within the modern movement. Yet in his late book, *Was bedeutet die moderne Kunst*, he will characterize *Kairuan* itself as "expressionistisch-sensitiv." Hausenstein 1949, p. 9, note 10.

¹¹⁶ Hausenstein 1921 pp. 106–07. "Mit Antike, Rom, Renaissance hat der Stil, der diese Kunst einspannt, nichts gemein. Auch kaum mit Barock oder Gotik. Das Impressionistische, das ihm eingehaftet ist, gibt nicht den Ausschlag. Eher hat der Stil so entfernte wie unbewußte Gemeinschaft mit primitiven Zeichenkünsten: mit dem Ductus vorgeschichtlicher Ritzungen auf Renttierschaufeln, Mammutzähnen; mit frühchristlichen Signeten; mit Pentagrammen der Magier; mit Zeichen der Kabbalisten; mit Kerben [...] auf Runenstäben. Allein auch so ist die Herkunft dieses überaus persönlichen Stils nicht erklärt. So sind Analogien angedeutet, die vielleicht dem Mißtrauischen das Phänomen legitimer machen. Es genügt auch nicht, auf das zeitgenössische Tun Picassos oder gar auf Abwandlung und Erstarrung seiner glänzenden Initiative im Schulgedanken des Kubismus hinzudeuten. [...] Die Herkunft liegt gerade in der Unbeirrtheit der Person; in der Abriegelung

aller Einflüsse; in dem Wegbiegen der Überlieferung und Gemeinschaft; in der Vollkommenheit der Vereinsamung. Macht in der Ähnlichkeit mit historischen und zeitgenössischen Eigentümlichkeiten sich ein Objektives geltend, ein Auswachsen über das Maß des Subjektiven, so ist dies Objektive ein Überschuß, ein Glück, doch nicht die Quelle der Bemühung."

¹¹⁷ Hausenstein 1921, p. 67. "Es entstand, unfähig, sich am Überlieferten zu orientieren, im Tiefsten verloren und im Tiefsten gewiß, wieder eine Kunst von magischem Wesen."

¹¹⁸ The earliest documented mention of it is in Klee's postcard to Hausenstein of May 22, 1918, in which he promised to send him the requested biographical material soon.

Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach.

¹¹⁹ The document was published for the first time in Klee, *Tagebücher*, pp. 504–517.

¹²⁰ Klee, *Tagebücher*, p. 504. "Ist zur Hälfte Schweizerin (Basel). Ihre übrige Abstammung ist nicht völlig geklärt, sie kañ über Südfrankreich orientalisches sein." In a draft for this statement Klee did not mention the possible oriental origin. He wrote: "Ihre französische Abstammung ist nicht völlig geklärt, sie kañ über Südfrankreich sein." But a section of the page between "Südfrankreich" and "sein," wide enough to accommodate three or more words, has been cut out of the sheet. See *ibid.*, p. 482.

¹²¹ Hausenstein, *Kairuan* Draft B, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach, pp. 10–11. "Ein ferner Horizont wird sichtbar. Eine Welt von großen Katzen und von Arbeitern an der Küste Nordafrikas, die bunte Matten flächten und dabei an Allah und an nicht denken. Haben Sie – so fragt man ihnen [sic] – arabisches Blut? Seine Mutter gehört mit allerlei Fäden nach Afrika."

¹²² Hausenstein, *Kairuan*, draft A, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach, p. 5. "Eine exotische Assoziation spielt mit, gibt der Schrift und Malerei gewisse exotische Anzüglichkeiten. Man weiß ja auch nicht *genaues* vom Blut. Ist er Araber oder

nicht? Ist er es nicht, so liegt freilich eine *Wahlverwandtschaft* vor. Dann malt er, *als wäre er Orientale*." Original emphasis.

¹²³ Hausenstein 1921, p. 28. "Dieser Mensch ist nicht von hier. Die Blässe des hohen Kopfes ist das in nordischen Kellern ausgebleichte Braun eines arabischen Mannes."

¹²⁴ Ibid. "Aber man könnte den Menschen auch ganz anders gekleidet denken: in einen weißen Burnus gehüllt, das Antlitz von weißem Tuch umrahmt und überschattet. Denn diesem wenig bewegten Körper scheint die schlafende Fülle unendlicher Schnelligkeiten einverleibt. Löse diesen vom Geist und von Gelüsten gezüchtigten Körper, setz ihn auf einen weißen Hengst mit rosenroten Lefzen oder zwischen die Höcker eines Kamels, öffne dem Entwöhnten Wege vor dem Atlas, Dünen der Wüste – und siehe, er wird zuhause sein: flüchtig, schießend, dem damasziierten Säbel bald gewachsen." Thanks to Luise Mahler for pointing out to me that there are no two-humped camels in North Africa. Two humps are a feature of the Bactrian camels of Asia. This is one more instance of Hausenstein's free-floating orientalist fantasy.

¹²⁵ Ibid., p. 29. "Kein Zufall, daß der Sohn der schönen Basler Mutter mit dem rätselhaften Hintergrund von einer afrikanischen Reise erzählen kann. Es war keine beliebige schöne Reise bis an den Rand des schwarzen Kontinents. Sondern es war eine Ausfahrt des Menschen zu sich selbst. Sie mußte sein, denn ihrer bedurfte er, um sich zu fassen."

¹²⁶ Ibid., pp. 29–30. "Schiebt nun auf der Tafel des Flügels sich Blatt über Blatt, eins ums andre mit wunderlichen Zeichen bedeckt, die keiner Gewöhnung des Urteils entsprechen, so ahnt die Betrachtung jählings einen Zusammenhang, der vieles aufklärt. Von diesem arabischen Schädel behext verlangt sie alsbald nichts andres als Arabesken: Bänder aus Farbe, die durcheinander laufen; Vieldeutigkeit, die nur in Ornamenten Gestalt gewinnen kann – denn die Gläubigen des Propheten vermeiden die Abbildung der menschlichen Gestalt, ja der Dinge, und sie begnügen sich mit dem Rhythmus der

Verzierungen, gewohnt, in ihnen den Tiefsinn des Lebens aufzuschreiben."

¹²⁷ I refer to the recent incident at Hamline University in St. Paul, Minnesota, where an art history professor showed a medieval image of the Prophet to her class, bringing a charge of Islamophobia from a Muslim student. The professor, an adjunct, was subsequently fired, igniting a controversy over academic freedom. See: <https://news.artnet.com/art-world/professor-terminated-art-history-paintings-muhammad-2238922> (last accessed September 26, 2023).

¹²⁸ On these works, see Benjamin R., 2014, pp. 232–239.

¹²⁹ Hausenstein, Kairuan Draft A, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach, p. 1. "Ausgehn vom 'Untergang des Abendlandes': keine Gegenstände, keine Menschen."

¹³⁰ Spengler 1920, p. 255. Cf. Öhlschläger 2000, pp. 123–126, who proposes that Hausenstein's orientaling of Klee is indebted to Wilhelm Worringer's characterization of "der orientalische Mensch" in *Formprobleme der Gotik* (1912).

¹³¹ Spengler 1920, pp. 307–308.

¹³² Ibid., p. 306.

¹³³ Hausenstein 1921, pp. 7, 20, 30, 67, 127, 134. Spengler identified not only Islam but also early Christianity with the magian soul. Spengler 1920, pp. 256–257, 264 et passim. Might this be Hausenstein's reason for choosing as front and back cover illustrations not works by Klee but images from an eleventh-century illuminated Italian manuscript from the Benedictine monastery of Monte Cassino of a ninth-century text, Rabanus Maurus's *De rerum naturis* (The nature of things)? Hausenstein discussed it in an article, "Seltsame Miniaturen," published in the journal *Genius* in 1920. On this article see Bitar 2018, p. 230.

¹³⁴ On this fabled journey, see Benjamin R., 2015, pp. 95–183 and Baumgartner 2014.

¹³⁵ The Tunisian diary was probably entered in the same notebook as the surviving original diary from 1916–1918. A sheaf of pages roughly one centimeter thick has been torn out, presumably

destroyed by Klee after he completed his redaction for that period. On this, see my remarks in Haxthausen 1981, pp. xii-xiii.

¹³⁶ Entry of April 16, 1914, in: Klee, Tagebücher, no. 9260, p. 350. "Ich lasse jetzt die Arbeit. [...] Die Farbe hat mich. Ich brauche nicht mehr nach ihr zu haschen. Sie hat mich für immer, ich weiss das. Das ist der glücklichen Stunde Sinn: ich und die Farbe sind eins. Ich bin Maler."

¹³⁷ Entry for April 15, 1914, in: *ibid.*, no. 926n, p. 350. "Zunächst ein grosser Taumel, der nachts beim Mariage arabe kulminiert. Nichts Einzelnes, nur das Ganze. Und was für ein Ganzes!! Tausend und eine Nacht als Extract mit 99% Wirklichkeitsgehalt."

¹³⁸ On Klee's redaction of his diaries, see Geelhaar 1979b. As I wrote in my preface to *The Formative Years*, "Only the fourth and final notebook, which commences with entry number 966 at the start of Klee's military duty in March 1916, is in its original form. [...] [A] sheaf of pages about one centimeter thick had been torn out of the front of the fourth notebook. Three missing pages were almost certainly the Urtext of the diary covering the period immediately preceding Klee's induction." Haxthausen 1981, p. xiii.

¹³⁹ Baumgartner 2009, p. 133; postcard from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein, January 9, 1921, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach. "Ihr Buch hat mich sehr sehr gefreut, und ich danke Ihnen vorläufig insbesondere für die Gelegenheit, es als einer der ersten lesen zu dürfen." Klee obviously read an advance copy; the book was published the following March.

¹⁴⁰ Baumgartner 2009, pp. 133-134. "Die Überarbeitung und Reinschrift seiner Tagebucheinträge zur Tunesien-Reise, die Klee 1921 in Angriff nahm und nicht vor dem Herbst 1921 abschloss, kann in diesem Kontext als Versuch verstanden werden, die destruktiven Tendenzen in Hausensteins Buch durch die Betonung seines Selbstverständnisses als produktiver Künstler zu relativieren. Im Gegensatz zu Hausenstein, der Kairuan zum metaphysischen Erlebnis verklärte, aber die

dort entstandenen Bilder mit keinem Wort erwähnte, stilisierte Klee das künstlerische Erlebnis der Farbe zum Höhepunkt der Reise in den Orient. Seine berühmt gewordene Emphase: 'Das ist der glücklichen Stunde Sinn: ich und die Farbe sind eins. Ich bin Maler,' kann, so gesehen, als Replik des Malers auf Hausenstein verstanden werden, der Licht und Farbe' als Nebenumstände bezeichnet hatte."

¹⁴¹ Hausenstein 1921, p. 87: "Vom Standpunkt des Kunstgeschichtschreibers mochte nicht sehr viel mehr zu konstatieren sein, als Befestigung des Sinns für die Farbe." In the autobiographical chronology Klee prepared for Hausenstein he made minimal reference to this moment. He wrote: "Reise nach Tunis und Kairuan mit Moilliet und Macke. Über Italien zurück. Befestigung der Farbe." Klee, Tagebücher, p. 517. Hausenstein adapted this formulation. Klee's terse remarks left a large space for Hausenstein's imagination.

¹⁴² The work was *Ansicht von St. Germain (View of St Germain)*, 1914, 41, one of the more stylistically conservative Tunisian watercolors.

¹⁴³ Hausenstein 1921, p. 125. "Kairuan. Der Name ward Symbol für eine vielfache Erfahrung. Östlich war, zu erkennen oder bestätigt zu finden, daß in der Tat die Dinge ohne Wesen sind; daß sie als Schein verachtet werden sollen [...]."

¹⁴⁴ Hausenstein 1919b. p. 44.

¹⁴⁵ Hausenstein 1921, p. 16. "Das Objekt, nicht etwa verschwunden, weil es unsterblich ist, ward dem schweifenden Auge, das am Rande irrt, nur entzogen. Nicht das Objekt ist fort; nur die Sicht ist unterbrochen, durch Entfernung. Die Sicht – doch nicht einmal die Wirkung. Denn Wirkung des göttlichen Geheimnisses besteht nach wie vor; nur daß der Blick durch Zerstreung und Abstand entwöhnt wurde, Wirkung zu sehn und sehend zu begreifen."

¹⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 16-17.

¹⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 94.

¹⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 103-104.

¹⁴⁹ Hausenstein 1913c. Interestingly, he republished this text virtually unchanged as a small book in 1920, with an altered title, and with the same house that would publish *Kairuan*

the following year: Wilhelm Hausenstein, *Bild und Gemeinschaft: Entwurf einer Soziologie der Kunst*, Munich: Kurt Wolff Verlag, 1920.

¹⁵⁰ Hausenstein 1913a, pp. 12–13. Perhaps with Hausenstein's book in mind, Spengler would ridicule the idea "daß der nackte menschliche Körper der vornehmste und eigentliche Gegenstand der bildenden Kunst sei Man hat, wie es scheint, nie bemerkt, wie selten diese Gattung ist, ein Einzelfall, eine Ausnahme, nichts weniger als eine Regel." Spengler 1920, p. 310.

¹⁵¹ Hausenstein 1913a, pp. 201–202.

¹⁵² Hausenstein 1921, p. 105.

¹⁵³ *Ibid.*, p. 109.

¹⁵⁴ Hausenstein mentions Richard Strauss's recently composed *Alpensinfonie*, a musical representation of a mountain hike. Hausenstein 1921, p. 110.

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 110, 113. Will Grohmann pushed back against this and other aspects of Hausenstein's Klee interpretation. See Hopfengart 1989, pp. 58–59.

¹⁵⁶ Hausenstein 1921, p. 112.

¹⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 114, 115, 116. "[...] sieh zu, was übrig bleibt. [...] dies ist, was sie Form nennen. Der Einwand ist nahe – man hört ihn voraus: Form müsse etwas realisieren. Sicher muß sie. Hier realisiert sie sich selbst. Über die Maßen ist sie in einer Welt, die der Dinge verlustig ging, ihr eignes Objekt geworden. [...] Form malt sich selbst. Form zeichnet sich selbst. Das Mittel emanzipiert sich, wie ehemals der Leibeigene. [...] Die Form von gestern ist Gegenstand der Form von Heute."

¹⁵⁸ He introduces the term *Malerzeichner* on page 46, but gives no explanation for it. Thereafter he sometimes refers to Klee as a *Maler*, sometimes as a *Zeichner*. Then this: "Denkwürdiges Ereignis, daß im gleichen Jahre 1907 die verzweifelt suchende Künstlerschaft zu den eigentlichen Anfängen des Ausdrucks durchbrach, der seitdem die unverkennbare und viel verhöhnnte Art des Namens Klee bezeichnete: einer Sprache der graphischen und malerischen Abstraktion." Hausenstein 1921, p. 65. On Hausenstein's use of this term, see Bourneuf 2015a, pp. 29–30.

¹⁵⁹ Hausenstein 1921, pp. 94–95. "Der Maler, der folgerichtig ist, muß heute ein Zeichner sein: Denn der Breite des Malerischen wird kein Widerlager mehr geboten, wohl aber wird die Spekulation der Graphik angespornt." Klee, stylistically pluralistic already at this date, did do painterly paintings, and several are reproduced in Hausenstein's book.

¹⁶⁰ In a letter to Hausenstein, Klee thanks him for "Ihr neues Buch auf das ich mich sehr freue. [...] Vom neuen Buch genoß ich jetzt schon die reizvollen Photographien." Letter from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein on December 23, 1919, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach. Klee does not mention the title of the "new book," but no other book by Hausenstein published at that time had illustrations except *Vom Geist des Barock*, with seventy-three full-page plates.

¹⁶¹ On this book, see Imorde 2013, Imorde 2018, and Bitar 2018, pp. 262–270.

¹⁶² Hausenstein 1919c; cf. Hausenstein, "Das Ganze," in: *idem* 1920c, p. 111–124.

¹⁶³ Hausenstein 1920c, p. 17.

¹⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 118.

¹⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 113.

¹⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 115.

¹⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 19.

¹⁶⁸ Hausenstein 1916b, p. 2.

¹⁶⁹ Hausenstein 1920c, p. 17.

¹⁷⁰ Hausenstein 1919/1920, p. 124.

¹⁷¹ Hausenstein 1920d, p. 180.

¹⁷² *Ibid.*, pp. 310–311. Note that in this instance he has revised his verdict on Expressionism since "Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick." It was evidently not "dead" after all.

¹⁷³ Hausenstein is repeating, with new coordinates, the error he had made before the war, namely reading style as a predictor of a fundamental change in *Weltanschauung* and ultimately in society. At that time he interpreted the emergent anti-naturalistic styles as a sign of the imminent triumph of socialism. Now that religion had supplanted sociology as his focus (see above, note 77), he sees painterliness in a handful of artists as an early sign of a return to nature, religion, and wholeness. He was wrong

again! On Hausenstein's earlier theory, see Haxthausen 1990, pp. 178–180.

¹⁷⁴ Hausenstein 1920a. A notice at the end of the book lists two recently published books by him plus *Kairuan*, which was "in preparation."

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 18.

¹⁷⁶ Hausenstein 1921, p. 122.

¹⁷⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 126.

¹⁷⁸ For a detailed discussion of this event, see Bourneuf 2022, pp. 45–48.

¹⁷⁹ As Hausenstein described it, the Germans, "in demselben Augenblick, in dem sie den Krieg verloren hatten, sich auf den Isenheimer Altar stürzten wie Verdurstende auf die Quelle des Lebens." Hausenstein 1919a, pp. 107–108.

¹⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 63.

¹⁸¹ Hausenstein 1921, p. 127. "Aber es scheint, als wäre das Phänomen zyklisch. Klee: der Name wächst über das Persönliche ins Symptom der Zeit und bezeichnet die Wiederkehr des Moments, der das alte Dogma und die beständigen Dinge verlor, das Aenigmatische aufstellt und des neuen Dogmas, vielleicht der neuen Wirklichkeit gewärtig ist."

¹⁸² Johann Konrad Eberlein was the first commentator to note this relationship. See Eberlein 2011, pp. 55–58.

¹⁸³ Hausenstein 1921, p. 128. "Auch sind einige Maler, denen die Dinge schon wieder gegeben sind. Sie haben den Intervall des Metaphysischen zu einem Dogma fortentwickelt. Sie glauben den Schöpfer – glauben ihn mit katechetischer Strenge, den Künstlern des Barock oder den Nazarenern ähnlich, inmitten der Entgegenständlichung und Entmenschung dieses Zeitalters. Damit ist ihnen die Welt wieder auferstanden: die alte Welt, jedoch so neu, wie die alte Welt nach Christus dieselbe und den- noch eine neue, mit neuen Kräften auf schier zweitausend Jahre, gewesen ist. [...] Das Objekt, trotz allem unsterblich, [...] begann vielleicht dem heimkehrenden Auge wieder sichtbar zu sein."

¹⁸⁴ Heinz Brüggemann, who writes at length on Hausenstein, Klee, and the Isenheim Altar, wrongly assumes that Hausenstein includes Klee in this group. See Brüggemann, p. 334.

¹⁸⁵ Yet, for all his praise, Hausenstein never dedicated a journal article or book to Kokoschka. His commentary from these years is limited to brief passages in his books on Grünewald, the Baroque, both versions of "Die Kunst in diesem Augenblick" and the second and third editions of *Die bildende Kunst der Gegenwart*. I suspect Hausenstein's claims for Kokoschka as the future of painting were a result of his flawed, wishful historiographic soothsaying than of a genuine enthusiasm for his art.

¹⁸⁶ Hausenstein 1921, p. 130. "Um Dinge zu malen, schaubare, einfache, gemeinsame, brauchte heute der Bildende nur diese Gewißheit: daß sie Natur, dennoch und wieder Natur und endlich Gottes Geschöpfe sind. [...] / Gewißheit, die in Sicht zu stehn scheint. Der Malerzeichner Klee ist das Bild des Augenblicks, der solcher Gewißheit vorangehn muß. Sein Tun steht zwischen der Historie der gestrigen Dinge, der Leere der heutigen und der ersehnten, noch nicht ergriffenen Fülle der Dinge von morgen. Sein Malen und Zeichnen ist der psychologische Augenblick zwischen den Zuständen. Dem Verlästerten, der ein Martyrium trug, danken wir das Bewußtsein von der Situation und einen großen Teil des Suchens nach der Erlösung."

¹⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 129. "[...] das radikalste Kennzeichen zeitgenössischer Verfassung, die den Kirchen fremd, dennoch frommen Herzens ist; die den Dingen mit Mißtrauen begegnet, weil sie aus sich allein nichts sind; die aber von Natur nicht mehr genug, von Gott noch nicht so viel weiß, daß sie das Zutrauen haben könnte, Dinge zu malen [...]."

¹⁸⁸ Brüggemann 2011, p. 338. For commentary on Brüggemann, see Bourneuf 2022, pp. 108–110.

¹⁸⁹ For a detailed account of Quaytman's discovery, see Bourneuf 2022, pp. 1–6. See also Quaytman 2015, pp. 35–41.

¹⁹⁰ In the year after he executed *Angelus Novus*, Klee mounted a watercolor, *Das Pathos der Fruchtbarkeit* (*The Pathos of Fertility*), 1921, 130, on the verso of a lithograph by Paul Rohrbach, but in contrast to the Luther engraving beneath *Angelus Novus*, nothing of the original image is

visible. The work belongs today to the collection of the Metropolitan Museum of Art, see: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/483145> (last accessed September 25, 2023).

¹⁹¹ Bourneuf 2022, p. 6.

¹⁹² Ibid., pp. 62, 66.

¹⁹³ Ibid., p. 66. See also ibid., pp. 97–100.

¹⁹⁴ *Angelus Novus* was not included in an exhibition again until it was shown by the Israel Museum in June 1990, to which it was bequeathed by Benjamin's friend Gershom Scholem, in an exhibition of twentieth-century works on paper from its own collection. It owes its fame to the surge of interest in Benjamin's writings that began in the late 1950s. In 1966, Suhrkamp Verlag titled its first paperback edition of Benjamin's selected writings *Angelus Novus: Ausgewählte Schriften*. For an excellent, richly contextualized discussion of Benjamin's "idiosyncratic and shifting conception of the *Angelus*", see Bourneuf 2022, pp. 69–103, 105–111.

¹⁹⁵ Letter from Paul Klee to Wilhelm Hausenstein, December 23, 1919, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach. "Das Grünewald Buch habe ich jetzt mit größtem Interesse gelesen. Es ist bei allem Reichtum sehr sachlich gehalten." Bourneuf mentions that the book was in Klee's library, but evidently did not see his unpublished letter to Hausenstein recording his reaction to it. See Bourneuf 2022, p. 42.

¹⁹⁶ Hausenstein 1919a., p. 102. Hausenstein stressed what he saw as the "baroque element" in Grünewald. In Grünewald's time, as in the Baroque, "handelte es sich ja darum, das Religiöse nicht als etwas Historisches zu konservieren, sondern es aus dem neuen Augenblick heraus auf ganz neue Weise aktuell zu machen." Ibid., p. 95.

¹⁹⁷ Hausenstein used the phrase in his notice in the *Münchner Neueste Nachrichten*, where he argued against Klee's appointment to the Stuttgart Academy. In *Kairuan* he makes several references to Klee's subjectivity. See Hausenstein 1921, pp. 101, 102, 103 et passim.

¹⁹⁸ In his allegorical reading, Benjamin would write of the angel: "His face is turned toward

the past." Benjamin W., 2003, p. 392. Klee might reasonably have retorted: no, it is not the angel who is turned toward the past (he actually casts his eyes to the side), but Hausenstein, his reactionary views signified by the overlaid image of Luther.

¹⁹⁹ Worth mentioning is a passage in Adalbert Stifter's story "Primel" (Primrose), which was in Klee's personal library, that possibly may have partly inspired his title. Stifter, describing the artistic process, writes of a painter: "der sieht den Finger Gottes aus den toten Farben wachsen, und was er doch selber gemacht hat, scheint ihm nun nicht bloß ein fremdes Gesicht, sondern auch eine fremde Seele, der er Achtung schuldig ist, – und öfters mag es geschehen, daß mit einem leichten ungefähren Zug des Pinsels plötzlich ein *neuer Engel* in die Züge tritt, davor er fast erschrickt und von Sehnsucht überkommen wird [my emphasis]." Stifter 1905, p. 33. Stifter describes an open-ended artistic process that has things in common with Klee's account of his own artistic process in his 1924 lecture at the Kunstverein Jena.

²⁰⁰ "Lieber Herr Doctor [sic]" was Klee's usual salutation in his correspondence with Hausenstein up to 1921. In a letter of January 7, 1921 (Deutsches Literaturarchiv Schiller-Nationalmuseum, Marbach), after receiving an advance copy of *Kairuan*, he now addressed Hausenstein as "lieber Freund."

²⁰¹ Letter from Wilhelm Hausenstein to Paul Klee, May 1920, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, inv. no. SFK Ko P Hau 10. "Lieber Herr Klee / ich möchte aus der Ausstellung (die prachttvoll ist) die Auswahl der Abbildungen für das Buch treffen, im Lauf dieser Wochen. Nun wird es darauf ankommen, die ausgewählten Sachen (über die ich mit Ihnen natürlich gern noch sprechen möchte) zu *reproduzieren*. Bitte sagen Sie mir, wann das geschehen kann. [...] Ich denke, am Schluß der Ausstellung?" Original emphasis.

²⁰² Hausenstein 1919a, p. 111. "[D]as religiöseste Zentrum des Isenheimer Altars ist das unendlich deutliche Lamm, dessen Herzblut in den goldenen Kelch springt."

²⁰³ Ibid., p. 12. "Die jeden Affekt paralyisierende Selbstverständlichkeit der Ruhe, mit der das Lamm sein Herzblut in den Kelch ergießt und schauend das stumme Haupt mit sanften Ohren hebt, ist dem gotischen Krampf der Drei zur Linken überlegen."

²⁰⁴ "Die Welt wird Regenbogen. Himmel und Erde werden Opal. Der Maler malt die Auferstehung Christi. [...] Mitten in einem nervös gestirnten Nachthimmel von schwarzgrüner Farbe steht oder kreist ein riesiger Lichthof: außen grün, dann blau, violett, rosa, orange, endlich gelb." Ibid., p. 34.

²⁰⁵ Three years earlier Klee had made just this point in a letter to Lily, reporting on his impressions of Augsburg's Gothic cathedral: "Ein Gang durch den Dom gestern Nachmittag hat mich von neuem von der Herrlichkeit dieser Architektur überzeugt und tief ergriffen. Die Bilder auf den Altären sind nur nicht entsprechend. Es fehlt ihnen durchaus die Inbrunst der Farbe. Wir können das jetzt besser, nur haben wir wieder keine Architektur dazu. Und alles kann ich doch nicht machen." Klee letter to Lily Klee, May 27, 1917, in: Klee, Briefe, vol. 2, p. 868.

²⁰⁶ Hausenstein 1919a, p. 111. "Inmitten des Ganzen stehe aber die Sichtbarkeit der Welt! Es hebe sich der Mut, sie zu behaupten, obwohl sie nur – oder weil sie – die Kreatur jenseitiger Macht ist! Es werde erkannt, daß die Metaphysik der Dinge, die ihre beste Schönheit ist, der vollendeten Schaubarkeit des Gegenständlichen nicht feindlich ist!"

²⁰⁷ The text was Klee's untitled contribution to the anthology *Schöpferische Konfession*, ed. by Kasimir Edschmid, (Berlin: Erich Reiss Verlag, 1920), reprinted in Klee, Schriften, pp. 118–122.

²⁰⁸ Ibid, p. 118.

²⁰⁹ Hausenstein 1923, p. 367.

²¹⁰ Ibid, p. 371. "Ich denke an Picasso und Braque und Chagall und Kandinsky – ich denke noch lieber an den Malerzeichner Klee, dessen 'ungegenständliches' (nur scheinbar ungegenständliches) Tun sich zur höchsten Schönheit einer farbigen und graphischen, einer dichtenden und musizierenden Irrationalität erhob, wo die Pariser die edlen

Gehege einer melancholischen Klassizität nicht gänzlich verlassen haben. Zumal auf den Blättern Klees sehe ich das Uneindeutige und Paradoxale der Programmatik des Expressionistums und anderer benachbarten Kategorien (zum Beispiel des Kubismus) wunderbar in die rätselhafte und tief produktive, elementare Selbstverständlichkeit vollkommener Kunst emporgezogen – dorthin, wo alles Paradoxale auf unerklärliche Weise mit sich selbst versöhnt ist. Den wenigsten ist solches gelungen."

²¹¹ Ibid, p. 373. "Was wird nun sein? Wir werden unsere Kunst in den einzelnen suchen, die mehr-als-expressionistisch sind: in den chimärischen Gesichtern Kubins, Kokoschkas, Beckmanns – in den freilich chimärischen Gesichtern." In a later (1924) essay on Beckmann, Hausenstein explained how he understood the chimerical: "ein exzessiv penetrantes, ein marterndes Wahrhaben der Dinge; ein Naturalismus ohnegleichen. Und noch einmal ein Nächstes geschieht: die Verwandlung der Dinge in Chimären. [...] Sie entspricht dem konstruktiven Sinn fürs Imaginäre. Der Verismus muß sich ins Metaphysische überschlagen." Hausenstein 1924, p. 70. He expanded on this in Hausenstein 1928, pp. 477–478, and ascribed the cultivation of the chimerical to the German character. "Der Deutsche ist ein Kind des chimärischen Geistes. Im Expressionismus hat diese Eigentümlichkeit des deutschen Geistes sich wiedergefunden: diese schicksalhafte Neigung zum Unheimlichen." Ibid., p. 489.

²¹² Hausenstein 1923, p. 371.

²¹³ Klee, Schriften, p. 122. "Auf Mensch! Schätze diese Villegiatur, einmal den Gesichtspunkt wie die Luft zu wechseln und dich in eine Welt versetzt zu sehen, die ablenkend Stärkung bietet für die unvermeidliche Rückkehr zum Grau des Werktags. / Noch mehr, sie ver helfe dir, die Hülle abzulegen, dich auf Momente Gott zu wä hnen. Dich stets wieder auf Feierabende zu freuen, an denen die Seele zur Tafel geht, ihre hungernden Nerven zu nähren, ihre erschlaffenden Gefä ße mit neuem Saft zu fü llen."

- ²¹⁴ Hausenstein 1949, p. 22.
- ²¹⁵ Ibid., p. 41.
- ²¹⁶ Klee 1999, p. 69. "Wir fanden Teile [...], aber noch nicht das Ganze. Wir haben noch nicht diese letzte Kraft, denn: uns trägt kein Volk."
- ²¹⁷ Letter of April 29, 1915, in: Klee, Briefe an Kubin, p. 87. It was around this time that a close friendship between Rilke and Hausenstein began. Rilke lived in the same Schwabing building as Klee, Ainmillerstraße 32, and in the third chapter of *Kairuan* Hausenstein mentions passing Rilke's apartment en route to that of Paul and Lily Klee. Hausenstein 1921, p. 21. Rilke was one of Hausenstein's two witnesses in his wedding to Margot Lipper in May 1919; their only child, Renée-Marie, born in 1922, was named after the poet. Hausenstein sent Rilke an advance copy of *Kairuan*, to which he wrote an extended and strongly affirmative response on February 23, 1921: "Ich bewundere es sehr, daß Sie Mittel gefunden haben, die Bedingungen, das Schicksal, das Verhängnis dieser (wie ich immer meinte, inkommensurabeln) Produktion darzustellen: Sie haben das mit einer Unbeirrlichkeit und Penetranz gethan, die mir nicht nur für die Arbeiten Klee's behülflich bleibt, sondern auch wichtig dadurch, daß hier ein so eigenthümlicher Durchschnitt durch die gegenwärtige Situation des Künstlers versucht worden ist. Wir haben das wohl alle kommen sehen, diese Abrückung der Ereignisse ins Unsichtbare, diesen an allen Stellen gleichzeitig vorbereiteten Verzicht einer Welt auf das sinnliche Aequivalent [...]." Cited in Migge 1967, pp. 79–80.
- ²¹⁸ Hausenstein 1925. "[M]it dem Namen Klee besitzt sie [die Galerie Neue Kunst Hans Goltz] ein Zentrum der Zeit. Ist eine paradoxe Formel erlaubt: ein exzentrisches Zentrum."
- ²¹⁹ Ibid. Is Hausenstein now finding in Klee a commonality with the "ejaculations" of baroque art?
- ²²⁰ Ibid.
- ²²¹ Ibid.
- ²²² Hausenstein 1928, p. 468. "Die natürlichen Dinge, das heißt: die in der Welt des unmittelbar Sichtlichen erfahrbaren Sachen,

die bislang den Gegenstand der bildenden Kunst ausgemacht hatten, wurden nicht mehr gemalt und geformt. In Bildern, Zeichnungen, ja selbst in Bildnereien erschienen diese Dinge 'sabotiert': sie schienen zertrümmert. Die Sabotage schien tief melancholisch. Die Bilder schienen über den zerstörten Dingen trostlos zu trauern. So viel war klar: die alten 'Dinge,' die natürlich gewachsenen, die sinnlichen, waren nicht mehr im Bilde. Die Tonpfeife des *Chardin*, der Apfel des *Courbet*, ja auch der Spargel oder Pfirsich des *Manet* war nicht mehr gemalt. Anderes sah man: Scherben – oft undefinierbare Bruchstücke; Sprengstücke aus einem Zusammenbruch; Splitter aus einem Weltuntergang. Solches sahen wir wohl am merkwürdigsten, noch merkwürdiger als bei *Pablo Picasso*, dem spanischen Pariser, oder bei seinem Landsmann *Juan Gris*, in den Aquarellen des *Paul Klee*." Original emphasis.

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